

On performing boundaries – a microprocessual view of creating boundary space

Argyro Almpantoulou^{*,1} , Kirsimarja Blomqvist

LUT University, LUT Business School, Yliopistonkatu 34, Lappeenranta, FI-53850, Finland

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ABSTRACT

To date, the literature has scarcely addressed the intricacies surrounding the creation of *boundary spaces* – novel organisational models that operate at the intersection of overlapping spheres or sectoral domains – and the microinteraction dynamics involved in initiating such processes. To address this shortcoming, we conducted a single case study of a multistakeholder initiative that engages in creating a boundary space. We adopt a microprocessual view and take a closer look at the focal individuals' boundary work, interactions, sayings and doings, and the emotions triggered by the process. The findings offer insights into the tensions underlying the creation of boundary spaces and individuals' performance of competitive, collaborative and configurational boundary work to resolve emerging tensions. Through our methodological choice of narrative analysis and ethnodrama, we show how the different embedded voices and meaningful silences in the creation process instantiate temporary and repetitive turns of boundary work, suspension and delay. We interpret these turns as both the result of the tensions and an explanation for why the tensions are not resolved.

1. Introduction

In this paper, we seek to advance the boundary space literature by focusing attention on the microinteraction dynamics involved in creating boundary spaces. Champenois and Etzkowitz (2018) define boundary space as a type of environment, or hybrid organisation, that operates at the intersection of overlapping spheres or sectoral domains (see also Caccamo and Beckman, 2022). Boundary spaces, such as startup accelerators or science and technology parks, are widely recognised in innovation literature for their potential to enable and facilitate cross-sectoral collective action and innovation (see *ibid.*; Champenois and Etzkowitz, 2018; Caccamo, 2020; Ungureanu et al., 2021). In fact, it has been argued that the spatial, social and symbolic processes of space are central in bringing actors together to interact and coordinate joint efforts (Räcker, Geiger and Seidl, 2024; Langley et al., 2019). Nevertheless, despite the importance of boundary spaces, their creation has remained relatively undertheorised. Research has devoted relatively little attention to early-stage, transitional periods when multiple and highly heterogeneous actors interact, and how these microinteractions, filled with tensions related to competing demands or conflicting goals

and perspectives (Miron-Spektor et al., 2018; Vallaster et al., 2021), can shape the creation of new space (cf. Furnari, 2014). Consider how delicate and complex the formation of mutual perceptions – or the 'meeting of the minds' as Drori and Lavie (2024, p. 26) call it – might be in multistakeholder initiatives, where collective action is just a glimmer in one's eye.

We argue that the tensions faced by individuals undertaking such initiatives when they are attempting to demarcate the boundaries of a space and of their own collaboration constitute an area worth further investigation. Boundaries in a collaborative situation create distinctions between what is to be included and excluded (cf. Räcker et al., 2024). 'Boundaries come to life through *boundary work*,' which refers to the practices through which boundaries are demarcated, crossed or modified (Stjerne and Svejenova, 2016, p. 1774, italics added; Palmer et al., 2025; see also Langley et al., 2019). Looking closely at individuals' boundary work also means looking at their everyday social interaction (Rouleau, 2005), their 'sayings and doings', and the emotions triggered by the process (Langley et al., 2019, p. 732). Since, to our knowledge, the literature does not explicitly address either the tensions individuals encounter in their attempts to create boundary space or the boundary

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: argyro.almpantoulou@lut.fi (A. Almpantoulou), satu.vesin@lut.fi (S. Vesin), pia.adibe@lut.fi (P. Adibe), kirsimarja.blomqvist@lut.fi (K. Blomqvist).

¹ The first two authors are listed alphabetically and contributed equally to this paper.

work they perform to resolve those tensions, with this study we ask the following research questions: what tensions underlie the attempt to create boundary space, and how does demarcating boundaries become a performative act to resolve these tensions?

When discussing creating space and boundary work, a focus on individuals is essential since it is not the organisations or other aggregate actors, but the specific interactants who negotiate and perform the work on behalf of their organisations (Grimm and Reinecke, 2024; see also Langley et al., 2019). In fact, strategy and organisation theory recognises the individual as the key strategic factor influencing collective phenomena, such as the emergence, evolution and performance of organisations (Barnard, 1968; Felin et al., 2012; Felin, Foss and Ployhart, 2015). However, individuals are ‘social actors interacting with other social actors’ (Thornton et al., 2012; Berger and Luckmann, 1966, in Furnari, 2014, p. 440). This notion highlights the importance not only of individuals’ action and behaviour, but also of their micro-level interactions, in understanding collective phenomena, such as the creation of boundary space (Furnari, 2014; Felin et al., 2015; Gray et al., 2015; Kouamé and Langley, 2018). Nevertheless, individuals’ interactions and the significance of micro-level activities and processes, or ‘what it is that micro-activities actually accomplish’, including the fine-grained qualitative work micro-activities require, are often overlooked in strategy and organisation research (Kouamé and Langley, 2018, p. 572). In this paper, we are interested in the microprocesses of boundary work constituting macroprocesses through which a space may exist (cf. instantiation in Kouamé and Langley, 2018; see also Gray et al., 2015; Alvehus and Crevani, 2022). Microprocesses refer to the ‘individual or collective processes and activities taking place at a lower level than organisational level’ (Kouamé and Langley, 2018, p. 561). Taking a microprocessual and boundary work perspective on space allows us to depart from a notion of space as a static ‘container’ with fixed, immobile boundaries (Steigenberger and Lübcke, 2022, p. 700; Langley et al., 2019).

Drawing on qualitative methodology, we zoom in on a case of a group of individuals, namely the Engine Room (ER), involved in creating a data economy² space (DES) in Finland. The DES was envisioned by the ER members as a space to help in identifying, aligning and, when useful, integrating old and new interdependent activities of data economy actors across different industries, public institutions, associations and communities in Finland. One of the precursor missions of the DES was to ensure that a shared not-for-profit public–private framework (i.e. infrastructure) would emerge and encompass a large pool of businesses and governmental and non-governmental organisations. The overall aim of the ER was to bring data economy actors out of their silos to collaborate across sectors. The initiative began as a series of open social information-sharing events for public and private organisations to come together online to create situational awareness and build new networks. To this end, the DES resembles a kind of boundary space (cf. Champenois and Etzkowitz, 2018) that was aimed at bridging sectoral boundaries.

In this study, we display a continuous (micro)process of boundary work (Patriotta and Spedale, 2011) that emphasises the dynamic and iterative nature of boundaries (Lindberg, Walter and Raviola, 2017). The organising work and interaction in the case represent a microprocess where the focal stakeholders collaboratively negotiate their professional, organisational and institutional boundaries while attempting to make room for a new boundary space. With our case study, we gain insight into the tensions underlying the attempt to create space. Through our methodological choice of narrative analysis and ethnodrama (Saldaña, 2011) and the resulting theatrical script, we reveal a

² The data economy is a global digital system where data is generated, collected, processed, analysed, automated and exploited by digital technologies to create economic value (European Commission, 2017; 2020; Sestino, Kahlawi and De Mauro, 2023). Many countries are investing notably in developing the necessary policies to promote but also regulate the data economy.

multivocal performance of tensions and boundary work. Our script showcases how the different embedded voices and meaningful silences in the creation process instantiate temporary and repetitive turns of boundary work, suspension and delay. We interpret these turns as both the result of the tensions and an explanation for why the tensions are not resolved. Yet, the tensions and suspension(s) emphasise not only the multivocality in the interaction and dynamics of the multistakeholder initiative but also, and more importantly, the performativity of individuals’ boundary work. With these findings, our study makes significant theoretical and methodological contributions to the literature on the microfoundations of boundary space, and on boundary work.

2. Theoretical background

2.1. Towards a microprocessual view of boundary space

In the context of the present study, we consider boundary space as a useful, yet sufficiently loose concept for understanding spaces that could serve as precursors to collective action. A boundary space describes a liminoid realm that is intended to integrate elements from different overlapping spheres or, in other words, to bridge sectoral boundaries (Champenois and Etzkowitz, 2018, p. 30; see also Shortt, 2015). If considered in the light of spatial configurations, such as the assemblage of actors, practices and physical attributes that are joined together (Stephenson et al., 2020), boundary spaces become potential hosts of organisational activities as ‘their boundaries allow specific actions to take place within them’ (Weinfurter and Seidl, 2019, p. 4). But how are such spaces created and by whom? Boundary spaces come into being through interactions and collaboration among members of a diverse set of organisations or communities that belong to different spheres (e.g. academia, policy and firms) (Champenois and Etzkowitz, 2018; Caccamo and Beckman, 2022). Taking a microfoundations perspective, Champenois and Etzkowitz (2018) have also highlighted the role of specific individuals, that is, boundary-spanners, in bringing and sustaining a boundary space into being (see also Furnari, 2014).

A microfoundations perspective focuses on how micro-level factors aggregate to macro-level phenomena (Felin et al., 2015; Palmié et al., 2023). The aim is to explain emergent outcomes by bringing the roles of focal individuals and other micro-factors, such as behavioural factors and routines, to the fore (ibid.; Barney and Felin, 2013). Microfoundations research has begun to enhance our understanding of the influence of individual-level determinants on collective phenomena, such as collaborative innovation (Bertello et al., 2022) and ecosystem emergence (Felin and Foss, 2023). Within microfoundations, a key area of focus is on situated microinteraction processes (Gray et al., 2015; Felin et al., 2015; Furnari, 2019). Interactionists have long highlighted that people form (and transform) meanings in social interaction (e.g. Goffman, 1959; Blumer, 1969). Therefore, when it comes to space creation, it is important to focus on how people do things together and how they collectively construct meaning within these interactions (Furnari, 2014; see also Becker, 1986), since ‘it is based on those meanings that people work and pursue organisational goals’ (Hallett et al., 2010, p. 495).

In this paper, we adopt a microprocessual perspective, viewing micro-processes as constituting (or performing) macro-processes where the link to macro-outcomes is ‘implicit and virtually simultaneous’ (see Kouamé and Langley, 2018, p. 572; Gray et al., 2015; Alvehus and Crevani, 2022). We focus on the microprocesses of boundary work constituting macro-processes through which a boundary space may exist, or in other words, on the individual actors’ interactions to ‘make room’ for a new boundary space (cf. Lunkka et al., 2021, p. 1272). Consequently, the spatial outcome is not static or fixed but dynamic, open-ended and incomplete, ‘performed through the simultaneous and excessive coming-together of multiple trajectories and forces’ (Beyes and Steyaert, 2012, p. 53; Beyes and Holt, 2020; Ratner, 2020; Steigenberger and Lübcke, 2022). In the words of Lefebvre (1991, cited in

Chan et al., 2019, p. 1), spaces are ‘socially produced through the performance of everyday practices, representations and imaginations’; hence, spaces are ‘abstract [...] broad, open and empty, inviting imagination to fill [them] with substance and illusion’ (vs place, in Tuan, 1975, p. 165).

Next, we turn to the literature on boundaries and boundary work (Langley et al., 2019) and the critical role of human agency in working for, at and through boundaries of space (e.g. Ungureanu et al., 2021; van Duijn, 2022; Bertello et al., 2022).

2.2. Working for, at, and through boundaries of spaces

In general, boundaries can be regarded as either tangible (i.e. physical boundaries) or intangible (i.e. mental and social boundaries) (Weinfurter and Seidl, 2019; see also Hernes, 2004). The literature also discusses professional, organisational and institutional boundaries. Organisational boundaries refer to ‘the demarcation of the social structure that constitutes an organisation’, that is, the demarcation of the resources possessed by the organisation, the boundaries of the sphere of organisational influence, and, more generally, the boundaries between the organisation and its environment (Santos and Eisenhardt, 2005, p. 491). Studies on institutional boundaries (e.g. Heinze and Kuhlmann, 2008; Sandmann and Weerts, 2008; Laudel and Gläser, 1998) recognise the institutional frameworks composed by different social entities, namely, internal systems of rules and policies governing but not fully controlling the practices and actions of their members, and that institutional boundaries become defined by the focal institutions’ scope. At the individual level, professional boundaries refer to the distinction between one profession or occupation and another, where, for example, boundaries regarding jurisdiction or ideological efforts serve as markers of difference (Lunkka et al., 2021; see also Gieryn, 1983).

We also acknowledge the different functions boundaries have when creating space (Weinfurter and Seidl, 2019). First, boundaries create distinctions between the space and its environment, which begins to give the space a sort of identity. The demarcation of the boundaries of a space ‘differentiates what happens in that space as well as what is excluded from it’ (Räcker et al., 2024, p. 5; see also Balcik et al., 2010; Lefebvre, 1991), and determines its reach (Weinfurter and Seidl, 2019). Second, boundaries serve as devices of order, that is, of regulating interaction within a space (Weinfurter and Seidl, 2019) and where and how organisational activities take place (Räcker et al., 2024), thus either bringing together or keeping apart certain activities (Langley et al., 2019). Third, boundaries function as thresholds for importing and exporting resources (Weinfurter and Seid, p. 24) and for collective action (Adibe et al., 2024).

When it comes to boundary spaces, they demarcate perhaps more permeable boundaries (Champanois and Ezkowitz, 2018) rather than directly distinguishing actors as insiders and outsiders like boundaries as lines may suggest (Gieryn, 1999). Boundaries can be considered both as barriers and junctures, depending on whether they inhibit or enable collaboration (Quick and Feldman, 2014). Nevertheless, despite the presence of boundaries, and the tensions they may reveal, they are often necessary to accomplish collaborative work (Langley et al., 2019). Hence, boundaries constitute ‘tools by which individuals and groups struggle over and come to agree upon definitions of reality’ (Lamont and Molnár, 2002, p. 168). In that sense, boundaries are not fixed demarcations or an inherent feature of a particular social context (Beck et al., 2024) but constructed and enacted in complex and often messy ways by human actors (Abbott, 1995).

Boundary work refers to human effort to modify or actualise boundaries (Lamont and Molnár, 2002; Quick and Feldman, 2014; Stjerne and Svejenova, 2016). Langley et al. (2019) offer a useful typology of distinct yet interrelated forms of boundary work, namely competitive, collaborative, and configurational boundary work. In general, boundary work highlights the critical role of human agency and

the temporal, evolving character of boundaries in organisational settings (ibid.).

Competitive boundary work focuses on the processes of defending, contesting and creating boundaries to distinguish oneself (themselves) from others to achieve or establish some kind of advantage over others (Langley et al., 2019). This type of work *for* boundaries dealing with isolation and connection (e.g. building alliances; Santos and Eisenhardt, 2005) becomes infused with paradoxical tensions and trade-offs; inclusion can only be defined when its opposite – the other(s) – is also defined (e.g. Bucher et al., 2016). What is noteworthy here is the dynamics of (competitive) boundary work. All boundaries exist in relation to other boundaries; hence, work on one boundary may influence another (Grodal, 2018; Langley et al., 2019).

Collaborative boundary work refers to groups’, occupations’ and organisations’ practices through which they work *at* boundaries. This type of boundary work aims at developing and sustaining ‘patterns of collaboration and coordination in settings where groups cannot achieve collective goals alone’ (Langley et al., 2019, p. 714). Different modes of collaborative boundary work – such as negotiating, embodying and downplaying boundaries – become prevalent in aligning boundaries and pragmatically agreeing on who will do what to enable collaboration (Langley et al., 2019, p. 715). In the present study, for example, an attempt to create a boundary space – a liminoid realm – accents the notion of *embodying* boundaries. Here, embodying means that some people may occupy positions of liminality (e.g. in their profession or organisation) where they themselves function ‘as thresholds between different groups’ (Langley et al., 2019, p. 718), and thus in a way incarnate boundaries. Hence, boundary spaces, or in-between spaces, relate to questions of identity and reveal the identity struggles of individuals at the intersections of organisational boundaries (Ollila, 2025; Kelly and McAdam, 2022).

Configurational boundary work is involved when not only intra-organisational spaces (e.g. Stjerne and Svejenova, 2016), but inter-organisational ones (e.g. Oldenhof et al., 2016) and spaces that spread across domains of activity (e.g. Cartel et al., 2019) are involved. In the different modes of this type of boundary work—such as arranging, buffering, or coalescing boundaries—agency comes from outside the existing boundaries and spaces being created to influence activities (Langley et al., 2019). Studies of this type of boundary work show how boundaries are deliberately manipulated to ensure that certain activities are brought together (e.g. arranging and/or coalescing boundaries) or temporarily kept apart (e.g. buffering boundaries) to enable effective or particular kinds of collective action (e.g. Bucher and Langley, 2016; Frickel, 2004).

The literature shows that boundary work efforts facilitate a ‘common understanding among actors involved in a joint task’, help to identify accountabilities within an assemblage of actors, such as who is involved, how and when (Räcker et al., 2024, p. 5; e.g. Valentine and Edmondson, 2015), and aid in resolving tensions in temporary organising (Stjerne and Svejenova, 2016). It is argued that a boundary work perspective is relevant in situations where collaboration is built from scratch (van Duijn, 2022; see also Beck et al., 2024). To this end, we acknowledge the importance of boundary work in terms of the dynamics of collaboration – which, in turn, influence work practices – when trying to develop integration across organisational contexts (Langley et al., 2019, pp. 704–705) and address tensions related to organising (Stjerne and Svejenova, 2016).

3. Methods

In this section, we elaborate on our methodological choices. First, we discuss our research strategy and explicate the logic of our case selection. Then, we describe the empirical setting and backstory of our case before concluding with a discussion of the selected data collection and analysis methods.

3.1. Research strategy and case selection

This study originated when one of the key initiators of the DES (I-10) contacted the fourth author. Their original interest was in how to scale ‘fast organising’ and advance cross-sectoral collaboration in the Finnish data economy. At the time, we felt that studying the process of creating the DES (in real time) could open a window that allowed a deeper understanding of how space is created. Tensions and boundary work, or a microprocessual perspective, were not a priori theoretical interests but occurred during our immersion in the data and our systematic data analysis. Thus, the methodological choices reported were not planned a priori; rather, they emerged gradually (see, e.g. Järvi et al., 2018). Throughout this and the following sections, we aim to remain truthful to the iterative and progressively focused nature of this study (Sinkovics and Alfoldi, 2012).

First, we started with a narrative inquiry in mind, as we wanted to explore the individuals’ stories in creating the DES. Focusing on the individuals was essential to capture the nuances of creating space, since it is not organisations or other aggregate actors but the specific interactants who negotiate and perform work on behalf of their organisations (Grimm and Reinecke, 2024). Narrative methodology, with its guidance for open, unstructured conversation with participants (Connelly and Clandinin, 1990; Riessman, 1993), enabled us to remain open and allow our participants to narrate what the DES was, or was meant to be, and how they saw their individual roles in creating it. While conducting narrative analysis of our data, we realised that this study was not only about the stories of the individuals but also about the individuals as a collective (cf. Weick and Roberts, 1993), a multi-stakeholder initiative, the ER and their boundary work. At this stage, we formulated our research questions to address what is presented in the introduction (i.e. what tensions underlie the attempt to create boundary space, and how does demarcating boundaries become a performative act to resolve these tensions?) and adopted a microprocessual perspective (see Kouamé and Langley, 2018). On that basis, we redesigned the study as a single, instrumental case study (Stake, 1995) – the ER – with 11 embedded units, representing the individual members of the ER (the progressive focusing of our study is described in more detail in section 3.4). We consider our case as instrumental in providing a deep understanding of boundary work as a performative act to resolve tensions involved in creating boundary space.

3.2. Empirical setting and the backstory of our case

The study starts from occurrences in late 2020. For four years, a public–private group of people worked to advance Finland’s data economy by building a non-profit public–private data infrastructure. At the time, many organisations were undertaking digitalisation projects but could not take full advantage of data sharing opportunities, because they lacked visibility into national and EU data policies and a proper infrastructure for data exchange. Two years of weekly group meetings resulted in a new initiative to bring the data economy actors in the country out of their silos and collaborate across sectors:

A couple of years ago, we noticed that there were so many of these projects that were not at all aware of each other. And the situation has only got worse. Our country is small enough that we should be able to see all the projects running and then support each other. That’s when we presented the idea of founding DES. To drive

interoperability and cooperation, and of course advance digitalisation faster in practice. Well, that didn’t go forward ... Now, I-10 promised to move onwards from their perspective and pilot this DES.³

By the end of November 2020, I-10, together with ten other people,⁴ had formed the ER⁵ and launched the DES. Initially, as a voluntary movement open to all, the DES was launched to help identify, align, and, when useful, integrate interdependent activities undertaken by actors across industries, sectors and communities in the country. The discussion within the ER was that, as a longer-term vision, the DES would ideally enable, and even accelerate, future collaborative structures, with ecosystems being one possible outcome, around the national data economy:

One of the themes of the spring events could also be ecosystems and their heightened significance in the data economy business. We revolve around this all the time, but it’s not explicitly talked about. It would be good to make this visible since companies in this country still carry out data-driven business development mainly alone, within the company.⁶

Both as individuals and representatives of their organisations, ER members were uncertain about all the projects and the roles different actors played in the field. Given this uncertainty, moving forward appeared to be difficult, as the ER members did not know what had already been done, what was currently occurring, and how those things and themes related to each other:

Every day, you hear of a new initiative that you haven’t heard of before.⁷

In November–December 2020, the ER organised the first set of DES events with the idea of creating and testing a space where cross-sectoral actors could come together to share information, create situational awareness and network. In the invitation to the first DES event, they asked their networks to spread the word and come and test it.

The ER’s launch of DES events was successful: the first three events attracted approximately 100 participants each. After the experimental phase of DES events in December, I-10 withdrew from their leading role as one of the key initiators and passed the administrative baton to I-11, a project manager from the National Agency (NA). The NA was considered a politically neutral organisation to coordinate the DES’s activities after its launch. Other changes to the composition of the ER were made to sustain the DES’s viability and ensure its core features remained relevant and interesting to a wide range of stakeholders (for more on the changes in the composition of the ER, see Tables 1 and 2). Due to the lack of resources, the number of events was reduced from every two weeks to once per month, as the ER discovered the challenges to maintaining the kind of volunteerism that had kick-started the DES.

The change in the coordinator of the practical work regarding the DES and the events also brought a change in who facilitated the meetings of the ER members. These changes caused discord within the ER, which had previously spoken with a single voice despite being a multi-stakeholder initiative, and individuals in the organising group began voicing their own, sometimes conflicting, opinions. As a result, the

³ Direct quotes from the first-round interview with I-1.

⁴ Note that 11 individuals initially formed the ER, but some did not continue after the piloting of the events, and five others joined afterwards. They were all interviewed, some twice. The analysis was mostly constructed based on the second-round interviews and other interactional data. See Table 2 for the background of the informants and their presence in the different data sets.

⁵ The name often used by the organising group of the DES when referring to themselves as a group. In addition to the ‘ER’, the group sometimes referred to themselves as the ‘work fist’, the ‘core group’, and the ‘working group’.

⁶ Direct quote from I-7’s email to the ER on 17th of December.

⁷ Direct quote from I-10’s email invitation to the first three DES events.

Table 1
Data sources and use in the analysis.

Data source	Type of data and use in the analysis
Interviews: <i>First round of interviews during December 2020 (6 h)</i> <i>Interviews with two informants during March 2021 (1,5h)</i> <i>Second round of interviews during April 2021 (6 h)</i>	A total of 13 h 30 min; 96 pages of transcripts. Type: Eleven preliminary interviews with those ER members, who were part of initially launching DES in November–December 2020. In the first interview round, five interviewees were not part of the ER at the time of the second round of interviews. (SEE Table 2 for more details on the informants' presence across data sources). Use: To deepen our contextual understanding of the broader data economy field in Finland, and the backgrounds of the ER members. Type: Two follow-up interviews with informants I-10 and I-11. Use: To follow up on the status of DES and plan the next steps of the fieldwork. Type: Eleven thematic interviews with the ER members who were part of the development of DES after the first three DES events. In the second interview round, there were six interviewees from the first round of interviewees and five interviewees who were not yet part of the ER at the time of the first round of interviews. (SEE Table 2). Use: To understand the ER members' varied perspectives regarding the development of the DES.
Meeting recordings: <i>First planning meeting for the workshop (63 min)</i> <i>Second planning meeting for the workshop (51 min)</i> <i>Workshop meeting (118 min)</i>	A total of 3 h 52 min; 23,5 pages of transcripts. Type: Interactional data. Video recordings from MS Teams meetings. A meeting between I-11, I-12, I-13 and two researchers, including the third author. Use: To learn how the ER navigated the tensions together. To corroborate interpretations emerging from the interviews. Type: Interactional data. Video recordings from MS Teams meetings. A meeting between the ER members and facilitator (I-13). Use: To learn how the ER navigated the tensions together. To corroborate interpretations emerging from the interviews. Type: Interactional data. Video recordings from MS Teams meetings. A meeting between the ER members and facilitator (I-13). Use: To learn how the ER navigated the tensions together. To corroborate interpretations emerging from the interviews.
Archival data: <i>Email correspondence</i> <i>Websites</i>	A total of 22 emails, ~30 pages. Type: Interactional data. Email exchange regarding planning DES and follow-up of the ER meetings. Use: To support, supplement, and integrate evidence from interviews and meeting recordings. Type: Publicly available digital output of the organisations involved in the ER. Use: To gain a contextual understanding of the broader data economy field in Finland, related national projects, and the ER members' organisations.

group started to experience challenges in developing the DES into a more established and effective concept in parallel with other data economy initiatives around the country.

Ultimately, we were able to follow the ongoing multistakeholder initiative through the preliminary ideation, initiation, launch and first development phase of the DES from October 2020 to October 2021 (see Fig. 1 for a timeline of the main events).

3.3. Data collection

Our data collection process comprised two rounds of open, unstructured interviews, video recordings from MS Teams meetings

Table 2
Informants of the study.

Informant	Age	Years of expertise in digitalisation	Background information on the informant	Presence in different data sources
I-1 = Terry	70–75	35	Works as a senior advisor with a non-governmental organisation, a fair data cooperative, which aims to enhance democracy in the data economy and enable collaborative projects through a joint public-private sector data platform and the “citizen data initiative”. Has more than 30 years of experience in digitalisation in the banking sector. In work role, aims to advance the self-sovereign identity to develop a universal, shared, and secure network for verified data—a method to ensure the accuracy of information in digital transactions. Knows I-10 for a long time.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> First and second rounds of interviews Meeting recordings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop meeting Email exchange: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planning DES and follow up of the ER meetings
I-2 = Wiley	41–45	25	Works as a director in a public sector organisation which advances technology development in industry and society. In work role deeply involved with the top digitisation projects that are going on in Finland. Aims to enhance societal impact through information dissemination and the creation of a wider community around data policy issues to advance sustainable technological solutions and competitive advantage for businesses.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Second round of interviews Meeting recordings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop meeting Email exchange: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planning DES and follow up of the ER meetings
I-3 = Joss	41–45	13	Works as a lawyer in a public sector organisation which advances technology development in industry and society. In work role, in charge of digital regulation on the national and EU-level and thus follows data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Second round of interviews Meeting recordings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop meeting Email exchange: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planning DES and follow up of

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Informant	Age	Years of expertise in digitalisation	Background information on the informant	Presence in different data sources
I-4 = Mason	55–60	25	economy projects closely. Works as a senior director in a public sector organisation which advances the development of digital infrastructure and digital solutions for the public-private sector. In work role, advances national and EU-level regulation by policy measures that support the data economy and ensures coordination at the project level for the more specific standardization of the data economy. Works as a CEO in a private company which advances the development of digital infrastructure and digital solutions for the public-private sector. In work role, aims to create digital innovations and educate on the data economy in a university.	the ER meetings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Second round of interviews Meeting recordings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Second planning meeting for workshop Workshop meeting Email exchange: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planning DES and follow up of the ER meetings
I-5 = Marley	51–55	20	Works as a specialist in a public sector organisation which advances technology development in industry and society. In their work role, embraces all the inputs for legislation and strategic thinking that come from the market, digest and contemplate them individually to understand what they mean in a broader context of the data economy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> First and second rounds of interviews Meeting recordings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Second planning meeting for workshop Workshop meeting
I-6 = Logan	35–40	7	Works as a specialist in a public sector organisation which advances technology development in industry and society. Alex is a newcomer in their present organisational position and role. Has a background in researching startups. In current work role, aims to	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> First and second rounds of interviews Meeting recordings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Second planning meeting for workshop Workshop meeting Email exchange: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planning DES and follow up of the ER meetings
I-7 = Alex	35–40	1	Works as a specialist in a public sector organisation which advances technology development in industry and society. Alex is a newcomer in their present organisational position and role. Has a background in researching startups. In current work role, aims to	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> First and second rounds interviews Email exchange: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planning DES and follow up of the ER meetings

Table 2 (continued)

Informant	Age	Years of expertise in digitalisation	Background information on the informant	Presence in different data sources
I-8 = James	35–40	6	advance technological expertise in businesses and develop collaboration between the public and private sectors. Works as a manager in a public sector organisation which advances small business development, education and technology development in industry and society. James is a newcomer in their present organisational position and role. Is also a newcomer to the ER in comparison to the other members. In work role, advances digital and educational affairs by networking and staying informed about various data economy phenomena.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Second round interviews Meeting recordings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Second planning meeting for workshop Workshop meeting
I-9 = Max	46–50	5	Works as a chief policy adviser in a public sector organisation which advances business investments. Has a background in the educational sector. In work role, aims to build data policy to advance innovations and the renewal of society with digitalisation and AI development.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> First and second rounds interviews Meeting recordings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Second planning meeting for workshop Workshop meeting Email exchange: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planning DES and follow up of the ER meetings
I-10 = Jody	61–65	30	Works as a senior specialist on ecosystems in a public sector organisation which advances the development of digital infrastructure and digital solutions for the public-private sector. In work role, aims to impact decision-makers, politicians, and experts in influential positions to have a better understanding of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> First and second rounds interviews Ad hoc interview Meeting recordings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop meeting Email exchange: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planning DES and follow up of the ER meetings

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Informant	Age	Years of expertise in digitalisation	Background information on the informant	Presence in different data sources
I-11 = Kirby	35–40	5	the prerequisites, rules, and building blocks of data economy. Knows Terry for a long time. Works as a coordinator at National Agency (NA), an organisation searching for innovative solutions to societal challenges, advancing fair data economies, facilitating multi-stakeholder collaboration, and enhancing long-term systemic changes. Joins ER when I-14 passes their responsibilities in coordinating DES events to I-11 after the first three DES events. In work role, aims to advance different NA initiatives, depending on its strategy and programmes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ad hoc email exchange between third author and I-10 • Interviews • Second round interviews • Ad hoc interview • Meeting recordings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First and second planning meetings for workshop • Workshop meeting • Email exchange: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning DES and follow up of the ER meetings • Ad hoc email exchange between third author and I-11
I-12 = Emery	35–40	n/a	Works as an assistant at National Agency (NA). Joins ER when I-11 needs help in coordinating ER meetings and the workshop for developing DES. In work role, aims to advance different NA initiatives, depending on its strategy and programmes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meeting recordings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First and second planning meeting for workshop • Workshop meeting
I-13 = Ivy	46–50	n/a	Works as a customer manager for an online platform company which advances social learning and collaboration in and across organisation, and initiatives like DES. In work role, supports the usage of the online platform in an optimal way. Here, helps the ER to facilitate DES events and helps I-11 to facilitate the ER’s workshop meeting.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First round interviews • Meeting recordings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First and second planning meetings for workshop • Workshop meeting
I-14 = LEE	35–40	4	Works as a manager at National Agency (NA) to advance fair data use in society.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First round interviews

Table 2 (continued)

Informant	Age	Years of expertise in digitalisation	Background information on the informant	Presence in different data sources
			Has a background in international networks. Steps out of ER when I-11 takes the responsibilities in coordinating DES events after the first three DES events. In work role, aims to advance different NA initiatives, depending on its strategy and programmes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Email exchange: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning DES and follow up of the ER meetings

between the ER members, and archival data, namely email correspondence and websites (see Table 1 for details of the data sources and their use in the analysis). The use of different data collection methods allowed us to corroborate our findings and therefore increased the trustworthiness of our study (Lincoln, 1995). Our immersion in the case started in October 2020, when the third author started to closely follow the work of the ER members while they prepared to launch the DES; for example, she participated in several of their meetings and informally chatted with some members. After the launch of the DES, the third author conducted a first round of interviews (Nov 2020–Jan 2021) with the ER members. This early immersion and the data gathered at this time helped us gain a contextual understanding (see also Shoter, 2006). During this time, we also gained an overview of the DES and its function, as the third author attended the first three DES events in November and December 2020.

During March 2021, the third author conducted two follow-up interviews (one with the new coordinator (I-11) and one with the key initiator (I-10)) to follow up on the status of the DES and plan the next steps of the fieldwork. We later used these interviews to support and supplement evidence from the other interviews and meeting recordings. Finally, a second round of open interviews was conducted with the current ER membership to understand the members’ perspectives on the development of the DES. We conducted a total of 24 interviews. The interviewees were selected based on their membership of the ER (see Malterud et al., 2016). In Table 2, we present background information about the participants in the study. The interview guide for the second round was discussed with I-10 and I-11 based on the two follow-up interviews. After these discussions, we decided to ask our participants to share their experiences and views on the DES, including its vision and mission in terms of its added value and how it should be developed. Our interviewees were also encouraged to reflect on their roles, the roles of others, and their overall engagement with the ER and DES. While we aimed to address the same broader themes with each interviewee, we left room to follow up on interesting themes that emerged during the interviews. The interviews lasted between 30 and 50 min and were recorded and transcribed verbatim to enable systematic analysis.

The third author also attended a workshop held by the ER at the end of April 2021 as well as two separate planning meetings that preceded it and were attended only by selected ER members. The workshop and planning meetings were video recorded and transcribed either verbatim or as summaries of the content. Additionally, we gathered archival data, such as email correspondence, to support, supplement and integrate evidence from interviews and meeting recordings. The third author’s engagement with the ER and DES since their inception allowed us to study the ER’s interactions in situ, facilitating an in-depth exploration of the microprocesses involved in boundary work (Langley et al., 2019; Lunkka et al., 2022). The video recordings of the workshop and planning meetings also supported this endeavour by enabling us to capture subtle

Email correspondence Oct 8, 2020 – Oct 4, 2021

Fig. 1. Timeline of main events.

nuances of the ER interactions (cf. Lunkka et al., 2022).

3.4. Data analysis

We began our analysis with an initial reading of the interview transcripts to familiarise ourselves with their content (cf. Braun and Clarke, 2022). While reading the interviews, we realised that the interviewees perceived the need to develop the DES differently. They were pondering the current function of the DES as a space and whether to maintain it as it was (i.e. community building and information sharing) or develop it into something else (i.e. cooperation towards concrete outcomes) while considering how they, as the ER, should organise (i.e. informally or formally). We discussed this initial insight with members of the ER, who confirmed it. Between our initial reading of the transcripts and undertaking the more systematic analysis, the members of the ER held and recorded three meetings (see data collection), whose potential for our study became apparent to us at a later stage.

We then deepened our analysis with a more systematic approach. We followed a thematic model of narrative analysis (Riessman, 1993; Esin, 2011), which allowed us to focus on thematic similarities and differences between our participants' accounts (see also the categorical-content analysis approach proposed by Lieblich et al. (1998)). At this stage, we realised that our participants were not only considering alternatives related to developing the function of the DES and the organisation of the ER but were also pulled between contradictory poles. We refer to this pull between contradictory poles as *tension*. Namely, we observed that they would, for example, discuss an idea and, in the next sentence, present a counterargument or a contradicting idea, using connecting conjunction words or phrases such as 'but' and 'on the one/other hand', or express uncertainty over these ideas, such as 'so, I'm not quite sure, but ...' and 'but I doubt it, yet ...'. At this stage, we constructed the following contradictory poles (thematic categories): *inclusive-exclusive participation*, *regulated-non-regulated agenda setting*, *coordinated-uncoordinated collaboration*, *defined-undefined roles and responsibilities*, *ad-hoc-committed participation*, and *designated-voluntary resources*. Our participants had diverse perspectives on these tensions; for some, the possible outcomes constituted more of an *either/or* situation, where choices were mutually exclusive (e.g. regulated *versus* unregulated), whereas others saw it more as a *both/and* situation, where

these choices were/could be mutually inclusive (e.g. regulated *and* unregulated).

Next, we returned to our initial insight concerning the DES's function and the ER's organisation and started to relate it to the more nuanced tensions. We interpreted that the tensions of inclusive-exclusive participation, regulated-non-regulated agenda setting, and coordinated-uncoordinated collaboration related to the function of the DES and the meta-level tension of emphasising coalescence (present function) vs. emphasising cooperation (envisioned function). Further, we considered that the tensions of defined-undefined roles and responsibilities, ad-hoc-committed participation and designated-voluntary resources related to the organisation of the ER and the meta-tension of emphasising informality (present form) vs. emphasising formality (envisioned form). Soon after these analytical insights, we realised that these tensions related to boundaries: not only the boundaries of the DES (e.g. who can join the space, and what happens in or is excluded from that space), but also those of the ER (e.g. who is part of the team and who will do what). This observation led us to research on boundary work and Langley et al.'s (2019) concepts of configurative and collaborative boundary work, which served as 'an intermediary step' (Langley, 1999, p. 701) in our analysis, providing new lenses for interpreting our preliminary findings and guiding the next steps of our analysis (Bowen, 2006; Charmaz, 2025). We interpreted the function-related tensions as concerning configurational boundary work and the organisation-related tensions as concerning collaborative boundary work (see Table 3).

With the notion of boundary work, we also realised the potential of our interactional data. We interpreted the meetings as reflective episodes (Krautzberger and Tuckermann, 2024) when actors are temporarily separated from their own organisations' (or personal) daily activities (Hendry and Seidl, 2003) to share time and space as a group to work on the boundaries of the DES and ER. Sensitised with the concepts of configurative and collaborative boundary work and with a clear understanding of the tensions as constructed from the interview accounts, the first two authors individually went through the meetings' transcripts, paying attention to both the content (i.e. what they said) and the form (i.e. how they said it). We paid attention to the participants' expressions and to stylistic characteristics such as the use of metaphors (Schoeneborn et al., 2019); for example, the metaphor of the 'life cycle' of the DES, and speaking about the DES or ER as a toddler, youngster,

Table 3

Tensions and boundary work in the multistakeholder initiative

In the table, the different arrows indicate either an ‘either/or’ tension (→/←) or a ‘both/and’ tension (↔).

Perspective to ...	Configurational boundary work regarding ...					
... developing the DES	... the function of the boundary space Emphasising coalescence (present function) vs. emphasising cooperation (envisioned function)					
	Inclusive vs. Exclusive participation		Regulated vs. Non-regulated agenda setting		Coordinated vs. Uncoordinated collaboration	
Emphasising coalescence I-2, I-6, I-9	... This is more important for those, perhaps the people of the outer circle, who are not quite in the inner circle and do not follow everything that’s happening here...the greatest value is in spreading information and creating a wider community of this kind.’	← ‘my team and I are so deeply informed about these key projects I think this [des] brings a certain kind of filtering and order to the noise . At least the most important projects are highlighted in a structured and filtered manner ... Like, this is important, this is valuable ... the role of the core group is to act as a kind of filter or a jury that sees which projects should be highlighted ... So that the spotlight is focused on the most relevant and important projects and that no shadow areas are left. This is somewhat how I see the core group’s function.’	← ‘this is very typical that we have a huge pile of these different kinds of projects and initiatives and new ideas ... and now they are all spread around, no one knows how to organise them and collect them together ...	‘There has been discussion about these subgroups and such ... →	... my intuition tells me that if we start to justify them too much, the whole thing will become fragmented, and that is a double-edged sword. They may work, or the fragmentation takes the edge away. I think I am leaning toward letting them emerge themselves if they become needed. ’
Emphasising both coalescence and cooperation I-3, I-4, I-5, I-10	‘It was important to get a complete picture of what the various actors are doing in the various areas of digitalisation, and I think it works really well for the purpose of networking and dissemination of information ... the value of this is the very forum we provide, and then there is also always the theme, which may draw new, curious people from outside the core gang , that close-knit core group. ... it’s clear that we should get the business world more involved ... ↔	... this is not a criticism but a statement that this is now more of a thing of an enlightened inner circle if there is still a little more of this sort of promiseware or slideware than concrete implementations. ... As long as we talk on a higher level and in terms that don’t resonate with the day-to-day business, it may be difficult for companies ... or it’s easy not to be interested. ’	‘ What type of cooperation can be done without any worries? Increasing this assurance in parallel to this thematic side of [DES]. So that it’s the way of doing things so that I trust all my partners ... ↔	... and when you have the content, then basically the projects will fly if there is an actual need and demand for them from the industry ... ’	‘What this concept [of DES] now needs, perhaps in a certain sense, is a more systematic way for some things, that at least we could have already used this network or this event to seek a direction or common vision around some themes ... the kind of subgroups that would then have a theme ...	↔ I am a bit ambivalent here that this [DES] is the place for this kind of subgroup and thematic kind of doing. The main idea and added value of [DES] is the kind of shared understanding and a bit broader discussion of what is going on in different parts and what’s the direction at the moment, what we should react to ... The current event serves its purpose quite well. Will something break in the concert if we start [setting up these subgroups]?’
Emphasising cooperation I-1	‘It’s easy to say that digitalisation is so important for the sake of competitive advantage and also democracy that it should be chaired by the state but not a state project but a public-private joint Project ... And of course, above all, agree that the intention of this Community is collective , the non-profit stuff ... →	... because this is such an important subject, it is [the state] who chooses the chairman for this entity. They can choose from wherever, but the state chooses.’	‘This [DES] would then be the manifestation where the state chairmanship would bring together the persons responsible for ongoing projects, the leaders, into a close dialogue to tell what they are doing ... →	... The state chairmanship is important here because if it were someone else, their own projects would inevitably become too important while other projects would get too little space. ’	‘[DES] is ... to organise the discussion, and it should be moderated a little differently than it has now been ... →	... there hasn’t been enough space for discussion. ’
Emphasising coalescence I-7, I-8, I-11	‘Perhaps, this sort of approachability ... The kind of low threshold,	–	‘In the best case, we can offer concrete examples. Like,	–	‘In these current [DES] sessions, there’s not that much	... that enables ecosystem building.’

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Table 3 (continued)

Perspective to ...	Configurational boundary work regarding ...		
... developing the DES	... the function of the boundary space Emphasising coalescence (present function) vs. emphasising cooperation (envisioned function)		
	Inclusive vs. Exclusive participation	Regulated vs. Non-regulated agenda setting	Coordinated vs. Uncoordinated collaboration
	like, you don't need to be anything or know anything to be able to come and listen. I think this sort of absence of hierarchy attracts in this, it's easy to come to take part.'	companies do not necessarily ... especially smaller companies, are not that interested in higher-level discussion of regulation or standards, for example, but more so in the business benefits that can be achieved from this, meaning the concrete business cases of how data has been opened, shared, and utilized for different business purposes in different industries.'	time for networking ... and I assume there will be a discussion whether there Are any separate instruments to be added to this concept [of DES] ... ↔
	Collaborative boundary work regarding ...		
	... the organisation of the multistakeholder initiative Emphasising informality (present form) vs. Emphasising formality (envisioned form)		
	Defined vs. Undefined roles and responsibilities	Ad-doc vs. Committed participation	Designated vs. Voluntary resourcing
Emphasising informality I-2, I-6, I-9	'I hope our role will remain about the same, so that we will not start running this in any way ... this is important that there is a balance, that [the National Agency] leads this as a neutral entity. And then we have people from the industry and from the ministry too and so on ... →	'Those people who come only to listen via [the conference call application], of those we have a lot ... →	... but when you take permanent measures, they require planning resources ... It requires preparation, facilitation ... Suddenly, it takes up quite a lot of effort. ... If we can answer that question of what the resources we play with are ... To this end, we need to have the resources in place ... '
Emphasising both informality and formality I-3, I-4, I-5, I-10	... and, in that sense, [the National Agency] is a neutral actor without vested interest which would create contradicting objectives in a way.'	↔ 'We also have a big goal now to make this public sector activity more effective. So, communicating these needs is essential. But it's also good that these don't revolve around public organisations that have their own role as agencies ...	'You could also think about changing the lead responsibility if necessary ... that one organisation takes on the whole [DES], it could be that the leading responsibility alternates ... ↔
Emphasising formality I-1	'The original task of [the National Agency] was only to facilitate, not to lead it. This should now be corrected because we are now in a situation where the general solutions are not progressing sufficiently.'	—	'Of course, this core group could and perhaps should be part of it in the future because it has now gained some experience on how this can work and how it shouldn't work.' ... this [DES] is an expression of national will, which then requires the state to express the will to finance this ... there should be that many resources that someone like a secretariat , who sees it as more interactive than what it is now, and then plan, let's say, short questions in advance, like, what is understood and what is not, and what is advocated.'

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Table 3 (continued)

Collaborative boundary work regarding ...						
... the organisation of the multistakeholder initiative Emphasising informality (present form) vs. Emphasising formality (envisioned form)						
	Defined vs. Undefined roles and responsibilities		Ad-doc vs. Committed participation		Designated vs. Voluntary resourcing	
Emphasising both informality and formality I-7, I-8, I-11	'When there is no formal structure or relationship in it, it can be more difficult to share the tasks ... ↔	... as long as this works, then maybe there is no need to force those Structures. ... And not in a way that it is somebody's post and obligation. '	... and there are people with different levels of intensity involved. '	↔ 'In leading a network or being (acting) in a network always involves the balancing act between what you want from the network and what you are willing to do for the network I understand the pain of [the National Agency] and think they should somehow formalise it so they can dedicate Resources to it. '	↔ 'We all recognise the need, the kind of pain from which rises the need to organise, regularize the kind of discussion, sharing thoughts, an encouraging forum, so, it has called for this kind of voluntary spirit ... a kind of voluntary spirit is what I recognise here ...

adult, or kindergarten aimed at directing the discussion towards some sort of shared understanding about what they had and where they wanted to go. After each round of individual analysis, we held meetings to corroborate our findings (Patton, 1999). We kept detailed memos of our discussions to make sure that all our creative ideas and decisions were documented (Charmaz, 2025; Saldaña, 2021), but also to facilitate our reflexivity and critical thinking (Birks et al., 2008; Mason, 2018).

Initially, our findings from the interactional data largely confirmed our earlier findings about the tensions and the diverse perspectives of the ER members. However, we felt that the data could do more than merely corroborate what the tensions were. Rather, the data provided a window into what exactly these actors were (or were not) doing to negotiate and resolve these tensions or, in other words, into how they were performing boundary work. At this point, we felt that our approach so far was incomplete, as it could not capture the delicate nuances of our participants' voices, laden with emotion, subtext and contradiction (cf. Cannon, 2012). We needed an approach that would also allow us to accurately represent and report the diversity of the voices in the ER (see Becker, 2007). Initially, we decided to stay with the narrative tradition and use the fairly new approach of composite narratives (i.e. combining multiple participants' accounts to tell a single story (see Willis, 2018, 2019)) due to its potential to 'afford the reader the ability to explore the "felt-sense"' (Wertz et al., 2011, p. 8). However, it felt that we were still missing the diversity of voices in the ER; it was our analytic voices that told the story, reflecting what Latour (1987) describes as the 'spokesman' effect (in Becker, 2007, p. 12). In addition, we found that we could not satisfactorily capture the more elusive elements in the interactional data, such as motive, emotion or subtext. For example, a 19-s silence in the workshop meeting struck us as particularly meaningful or salient, 'beg[ging] for an interpretation or analysis of its own' (Poland and Pederson, 1998, p. 294). However, our current analysis did not facilitate a deeper exploration or understanding of what that silence meant for boundary work. We needed what Kouame and Langley (2017, p. 572) call a 'deep dive' approach to our analysis, that could help us explore the meaning of those more subtle elements and enhance the representation (and presentation) of our participants' realities (cf. Cannon, 2012; see also Kouame and Langley, 2017).

Hence, we turned to arts-based methods, such as ethnodrama (Saldaña, 2011), dramaturgical coding (Saldaña, 2021; Cahnmann-Taylor and Siegesmund, 2008; Leavy, 2015) and scripting⁸ (Donmoyer and Yennie-Donmoyer, 1995). An ethnodrama is a written play script based on the dramatisation of a diverse set of data, which can include interview transcripts, email correspondence, field notes, etc. (Saldaña,

2011). Ethnodrama is an approach that aims to give an aesthetic shape while preserving the authenticity and integrity of participants' voices (Saldaña, 2011; Anderson, 2015). In practice, actual verbatim quotes from the data are adapted and edited to boost critical moments in the dramatic narrative. We believe that ethnodrama can facilitate the 'more fine-grained work' needed in the study of boundary work to 'authentically capture the sayings and doings that people engage in to influence demarcations shaping their social context' (Langley et al., 2019, p. 727). In organisation and management studies, ethnodrama has remained a rather niche approach, even though it has been gaining some traction (e.g. Starkey, 1999; Biehl-Missal, 2012; Woolsey et al., 2024). Arts-based methods, including ethnodrama, can open up new ways of thinking and theorising about organisations and management that respect multivocality (Rhodes and Brown, 2005; Becker, 2007). In our case, we felt that its ability to 'open up the narrative possibilities [to] create a dialogue between different conceptions of a particular organisational reality' (Rhodes and Brown, 2005, p. 473) could allow us to tell the ER's story more 'credibly, vividly and persuasively' (Saldaña, 2005, p. 2).

We continued our analysis with dramaturgical coding (cf. Cannon, 2012). Dramaturgical coding follows an abductive logic, as it involves both inductive and deductive coding processes (ibid.). The coding process proceeded as follows: initially, the first author reread the transcripts of the meeting recordings and inductively coded the text using a combination of in-vivo (participants' own words) and process (gerund) codes. Next, each code was assigned a secondary, dramaturgical code, following Bogdan and Biklen's (2007) strategy codes as adopted by Saldaña (2021). These included the participants' objectives (OBJ), conflicts preventing the achievement of these objectives (CON), the participants' tactics for dealing with conflicts and/or achieving objectives (TAC), the participants' attitudes towards the setting, others and/or conflicts (ATT), and the participants' emotions (EMO) and subtexts (SUB). This additional round of analysis with dramaturgical coding allowed us to gain insight into our participants' motives, which facilitated a deeper understanding not only of the participants' perspectives on the DES's function and the ER's organisation, but also of their actions (or inactions) and reactions in the meetings (and emails). An example is illustrated in Table 4.

To corroborate the first author's interpretations of emotion and subtext in the transcripts, the second author rewatched the recordings and noted her observations, which helped to further refine the codes. The code *SUB Suspending*, assigned next to the 19-s silence mentioned above, became a central part of our analysis and interpretation of the case. We decided to look for any other instances in our data that could be interpreted similarly. In fact, additional shorter pauses or silences were present throughout the recorded meetings, after which we found it particularly interesting or unexpected to note again a long silence (12 days) in the ER members' email correspondence, initiated by I-11, that

⁸ Not to be confused with 'scripting' in actor-network theory (by Akrich and Latour, 1992, in Lindberg et al., 2017).

Table 4
Example of dramaturgical coding.

Quote from workshop transcript	Dramaturgical codes
I-13: Should we now then go ahead and identify where there might be interest in taking responsibility?	OBJ 'Taking responsibility'
... I believe in enthusiasm and motivation as the driving factors	TAC Moralising
—many networks operate this way, especially ones that rely on a bit of voluntary effort. So?	TAC Invoking their sense of responsibility
[19 seconds of silence]	SUB Suspending
I-10: This is usually the moment when everyone raises their hands, when it's asked who would do something ...	OBJ Breaking the silence TAC Using humour/irony
[I-10 and I-1 laugh]	ATT Laughing

took place after the workshop. Only after I-11 sent a reminder did a few of the ER members react, but they declined to take any responsibility for developing the DES. Previous literature focusing on the lived experience of tension has discussed such short, temporary periods when work is suspended (e.g. Pradies et al., 2021). Particularly, studies have argued that such brief periods might be necessary for individual actors 'to readjust and reorient themselves' (Powley, 2009, p. 1299), but they can also be used by these actors as some kind of protective mechanism to minimise any long-term inadvertent consequences of quick, short-term decisions (Wilson, 2020, in Pradies et al., 2021). After sensitising our analysis with these ideas, we understood that *suspending* could be what sustained the tensions, explaining why the tensions persisted and remained unresolved, but also their outcome or result.

Next, we used a method called scripting (e.g. Donmoyer and Yennie-Donmoyer, 1995; Saldaña, 2011) to start building our script. At this point, we had a better understanding of what our participants wanted others to do (objectives), what stood in their way (conflicts), and what they did to achieve their objectives or deal with conflicts (tactics). Our attention to emotion and subtext also attuned us to the more internal perspectives of our participants (Cannon, 2012; Saldaña, 2021). We used all these insights to build the characters in the script (see the next section for more on the characters). To write the script, we relied on all the available data sources, following ethnodramatists who often do so not only to gain a wider spectrum of perspectives, but also to add richer dimensions to the story (Saldaña, 2011). Similarly to a process described by Saldaña (2011), we started by pulling out extracts from our data that addressed the same topic, which we then used to create an initial skeletal structure for our script. While deliberately assembling or putting together these snippets into plausible monologues or dialogues, we experimented with multiple arrangements and flow (cf. Saldaña, 2011). We decided to use both monologic and dialogic storytelling formats and included a variation of plotting devices, such as a curtain-raising prologue, soliloquy, choral exchange and climax (see Riessman, 2008; Saldaña, 2011). To build the choral exchanges, we used actual verbatim dialogue from the workshop as much as possible, as doing so simply felt like a more intimate, authentic and powerful way to narrate elements such as the story's climax (or anticlimax), that is, the suspending, and thus give the characters more realism and vigour (Hammond and Steward, 2008; Saldaña, 2011). Overall, we interwove our characters' similar and contrasting perspectives and mostly trimmed or condensed the original quotes to capture their essence but also enhance the dramatic effect, while making sure that we did not alter the mood of the story or our participants' unique voices (cf. Saldaña, 2011; Cannon, 2012).

4. The script: performing boundary work

4.1. *Introduction of the setting and the characters*⁹

This play – with all its acts and scenes – takes place on a theatre stage set up like an MS Teams meeting in an auditorium or amphitheatre view, fitting 13 people, framed by props¹⁰ as an online workshop meeting. Before being allowed to enter the together-mode view in the workshop meeting, the characters are seated in a waiting room awaiting their turn to enter the stage.

Kirby steps onto the stage ready and motivated to develop the DES, finally, together with the others in the ER. Kirby is followed by **Ivy** and **Emery**, who are here to help in organising and facilitating the workshop, which is about to start. The task of coordinating the work of the ER and DES has been challenging, but since being entrusted with this role and responsibility by **LEE** at the NA, Kirby has been learning a great deal about leading a network ... After six months, the collective goals of the DES are still not clear, and each member of the ER represents different views of what direction to take ...

Alex enters the stage with great enthusiasm and takes the first seat in the waiting room. Alex is passionate about what the DES represents among the data economy initiatives of the country, but he understands Kirby's difficulties in leading the ER without a proper structure and is here to give support. **Jody** steps onto the stage next and takes a seat a few seats away from Alex. Jody is inspired by the possibilities of the DES but is already somewhat detached from what the ER is doing due to a new digital transformation project. Jody has been thinking someone else should take the thought leadership of DES and the change it is trying to convey. Jody has done enough in the launch of the DES, but it seems that others have not realised that there is an intention to pass the baton to the NA and reconsider how much to participate in the ER's activities ...

Terry sits next to Jody in the waiting room with mixed feelings. Terry has been disappointed, even angry, with the direction the DES has started to take. Terry's face is doubtful. How is the NA using its resources, and is that new public-private data space project of theirs too high up the agenda? Yet, Terry decides to take part in the upcoming workshop to give the ER a second chance to align their various goals with the DES, hoping that this time they may move towards thinking about concrete actions ...

Max steps onto the stage with a well-meaning expression and a smile. Max is talking on the phone with a CEO who is interested in hearing how Max's organisation could advance their company's cause in the technology industry. Max is keen to see what kind of practical steps can be taken regarding the DES in the workshop and to talk about small business opportunities with **James**, who enters the stage next. **Marley** is right behind Max and James and almost bumps into them because his mind is on the newest ideas about how to develop DES events in practice.

Mason, **Logan**, **Joss**, and **Wiley** are the last to take their seats in the waiting room. They too want to have a say in this workshop. Their interest is in having an impact on the themes the DES advocates but interfering as little as possible with the practical work, as long as the DES survives and their goals are met somehow. They may be here because they want a sense of control over where the DES is steered or just because they want to continue to have a say about what it does.

Note: [*Brackets in the script with text in italics*] indicate the director's voice, which is not audible/visible to the audience. Each act starts with opening words, and each scene ends with an interpretation that connects the unfolding script with theoretical constructs.

⁹ Dramatised from the informants' presence in the data.

¹⁰ Or theatrical property, which is an object actors use on stage during a performance.

4.2. Act 1—IF it AIN'T broken, WHY fix it?

Act 1 showcases the multitude of voices – the different perceptions, priorities, even politics – in creating a boundary space, and how they are considered within a multistakeholder initiative. These voices start revealing how creating a boundary space that is as inclusive and uncoordinated as possible without any heavy top-down agenda while still demarcating it as something that might facilitate collaboration across sectors, is a tension-laden endeavour and requires *boundary work* by the focal individuals.

4.2.1. Scene 1—Scrambling things together at the last minute

[A curtain raiser; monologue by Kirby; speaking directly to an audience; spotlight on Kirby; other characters in the dark.]

Kirby: As a group of people, who sit down and think about the DES¹¹, the ER has become a rather demanding bunch to manage ...

Since Lee introduced me to them as the project manager for DES,¹² I've learned that these people have rather strong views about what kind of an influence DES could have, what kind of goals are important to keep in mind, what themes might arise, what kind of activities could emerge from this, and so on.¹³ But apparently, we're in a situation where people have a lot of visions, and yet NA should run the show.

When it comes to general organisational logistics, we at the NA promised to handle practical matters, like facilitating and offering an online platform for the DES because we initially got it pro bono. But it will eventually expire, leaving someone to cover the cost of maintaining that online space ... Perhaps no one in the ER has ever considered that?¹⁴

Obviously, they don't know the whole story.

We at the NA have been in survival mode for the past couple of months because we have our own project ... We are getting a new director, starting up new projects, and winding down old ones ... Unfortunately, we haven't been able to develop the concept or to run the DES events twice a month but only once ... We haven't had enough resources, but that must have come as a surprise to the ER members.¹⁵

We've organised the last few events through informal email threads. But it doesn't work if we just scramble to put things together at the last minute. I'd be happy to have someone to share the responsibility with. This is what we have and so far, nobody has come forward and offered their help so that DES events could be done, say, every other week. There are always lots of ideas, but someone else is expected to make them happen. Someone with enough time, money, and resources. Luckily, I finally got Emery to support me with the ER.¹⁶

At least we've agreed to have this workshop with the ER members. I hope it offers us a breathing space to think collectively about the future and next steps of the DES. With Emery, we approached everyone with the question of how the time in this workshop could be used to best serve our overall intentions. Ivy promised to facilitate the workshop with the online platform. We all agreed that the purpose is not only to reflect and refine the concept of the DES, but also to look for concrete actions that would go beyond the DES events.¹⁷

Oh, now they are starting to come into Teams for the workshop ... Got to go!

In Scene 1, we can see how tensions start to *decelerate* the creation of a boundary space and how frustration discourages organising work around the multistakeholder initiative itself. In addition, confusion around the boundaries of the individuals' and their background

organisations' roles, responsibilities, and resources hinders coordination of their collective efforts.

4.2.2. Scene 2—Whose perspective? Tensions are unearthed

[A choral exchange between all the characters except Lee, who is not attending the workshop; everyone in the spotlight]

Max: Hey, Kirby, before we actually start the workshop ... Is the NA committed to the basic costs that will keep the DES running? I mean, what kind of timeframe are we looking at?¹⁸

Kirby: Well, NA has promised to cover the costs of the online platform. But when it comes to other resources, it's hard to say. There are ongoing organisational changes ... For now, we have people, but it's difficult to predict further ahead. What exactly did you mean by resourcing?¹⁹

Max: Exactly that. The basic structure needs to function, for example, the NA provides the platform for the DES so that we all know this will continue until next Christmas or so. That gives us a time window to see where we're heading. Any uncertain phases need to be addressed separately. But let's revisit the resourcing in more detail later. This answer suffices for now.²⁰

Kirby: Good, I don't have more to add at this point anyway.²¹

Emery: At the NA, we have a new director who just started a few weeks ago and decisions go through him now, based on how he sees things. The intent is positive, but it's impossible to say what he thinks in the long term.²²

Max: Well, this has been an experiment, but it has shown that the reach has been good. The right number of people has been targeted somehow.²³ The DES has done its work on the event crowd and introduced something new and interesting to them. And since Kirby took over the practical work, the events have started to take a more stable basic form. The attendees know what is happening at the events.²⁴

Wiley: I remember that there were several hundred of them in the morning sessions. DES grew completely past the official system, from the grassroots up, without any kind of major investment in marketing. If the events have so many listeners, DES has succeeded well.²⁵

Logan: Sure, but enthusiasm was higher in the very beginning. But I guess that's quite normal.²⁶

Terry: Well, it's been a little disappointing that the discussion is not really ... it hasn't been given space, only a few throws here and there.²⁷

Wiley: Yeah, there've been ideas that we need to increase the pace again ... Then there are the resource challenges. Kirby, among others, said directly that they don't have enough resources now. I think that once a month is sufficient, like it is at the moment.²⁸

Logan: I understand that it takes an awful lot of energy, resources, and commitment to run this thing. It takes time which none of us have. Not even you, Kirby.²⁹

Wiley: The fact that the NA has taken on the role of facilitator is good. It suits them well, and they have the resources. Still, I wouldn't go as far as to make any drastic changes to this because this format seems to work. Don't fix what isn't broken.³⁰

Max: The experimentation has only been going on for a brief time. The current form and function of DES will live or die depending on

¹¹ Paraphrased quotes from I-11 in a meeting with the third author.

¹² I-14's email to the ER on 17th of December.

¹³ Paraphrased quotes from the third author in a meeting with I-11.

¹⁴ Paraphrased quotes from I-11 in a meeting with the third author.

¹⁵ Paraphrased quotes from I-11 in a meeting with the third author.

¹⁶ Paraphrased quotes from I-11 in a meeting with the third author.

¹⁷ Paraphrased quote from I-11 in the second planning meeting.

¹⁸ Direct quotes from I-9 in workshop planning meeting recording.

¹⁹ Direct quote from I-11 in the workshop planning meeting recording.

²⁰ Direct quote from I-9 in the workshop planning meeting recording.

²¹ Direct quote from I-11 in the workshop planning meeting recording.

²² Direct quote from I-12 in the second planning meeting.

²³ Direct quote from I-9 in the second planning meeting.

²⁴ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-9.

²⁵ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-2.

²⁶ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-6.

²⁷ Direct quote from the second-round interview with I-1.

²⁸ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-2.

²⁹ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-6.

³⁰ Direct quote from the second-round interview with I-2.

group dynamics and what resources are available in the future. We don't have the answers yet. So, as Wiley said, let's not fix what isn't broken, shall we?³¹

Terry: [Terry frowns] To me, this thing doesn't work now. It can't be just a presentation and then nothing happens, then the next presentation and then nothing happens. Our original goal of collaborating to create general solutions has somehow faded away. I've already discussed with Jody that we [air quoting] 'should then organise such working groups that take a general-purpose theme and then return to this issue'. We should return to the original idea that this is an expression of national will. The idea of a joint public-private data platform enabling collaborative projects hasn't been realised here. State leadership would be important here because if it were someone else, their own projects would inevitably become too important while other projects would get too little space. This must be a digitalisation project for the whole society.³²

Marley: The timing of this workshop is perfect for that. It gives us a sense of what transitioning to a permanent mode from the experimental phase means and provides tools for that. What also stands out to me is the national aspect. What do we, in Finland, want? What is the Finnish intention? Like Terry said, this was one of the original ideas of the DES, and perhaps we haven't done as much about defining a shared goal and direction for where we want to go. Part of it is a format issue. In the DES, we haven't used tools like the online platform that's been suggested in that direction. It's been more about what is happening and discussions around it, but not something systematic, like [air quoting] 'this is where we want to go', and then the DES would reflect on whether we are moving in that direction. For example, in a thematic session, we might decide more in a workshop format that [air quoting] 'this could be a good direction for Finland, or at least we are strongly aligned with this group'.³³

Terry: The resourcing problems of Kirby and the NA worry me. The original idea also needs the state to say it's willing to finance this. It's easy to say that digitalisation is important for competitiveness, and also for democracy, and that it should be led by the state. But it shouldn't be a governmental project—specifically, it should be a public-private joint venture based on infrastructure built on the secure network of verifiable data solutions, and it should also be funded.³⁴

Marley: Possibly after this workshop, we will have an outcome where, at least with this group, we agree on a direction, and hopefully that direction is more widely accepted. After that, we can reflect on whether we are moving in that direction. This could be one clear tool that the DES could offer. I don't know if *this* [said with emphasis] is the right place to define a Finnish vision, but this *could* [said with emphasis] be the right place for defining one and how to bring it up more at the DES events ... Perhaps the DES is one of those events where we aren't as international, but rather we focus more on the Finnish vision ... After all, that's what this was all about when we started.³⁵

Kirby: I want to pick up on what Marley mentioned ... I'd like to see some sort of lifecycle or evolution thinking for the DES. For example, what Marley considered, are we aiming for Finland's national perspectives in this forum? Could we, in this forum, collectively issue a statement in the name of this network? Is that the goal we're aiming for and what we want to grow into? This is the kind of lifecycle reflection I'm considering ... Right now, we're like a toddler. What's our teenage phase? What will we be when we grow up?³⁶

Mason: I like that idea, too. Growing the mass at the national level (with the DES) first, building the muscle, and then going to Europe. My

concern with the other international data economy initiative cohort is that we might see some isolated bursts of movement without enough muscle. Right now, we have these two-year-old toddlers playing with their blocks with their backs to each other, but if we could get them to play with the same blocks in the DES and build their own tower ... But let's handle this first phase at the national level and find funding mechanisms while also getting the stakeholders more committed to tighter cooperation. I don't believe we'll reach concrete solutions by developing everything openly on the table. However, by bringing all the key players together in this network, we could add value by ensuring there's no duplication (between these two data economy initiatives – the national and the international). We wouldn't start developing those concepts from scratch there; instead, we'd tailor the profile for them.³⁷

Ivy: There's definitely a need for a place where a smaller group can work together, and through working together, trust grows. Then, they'd be ready to share trade secrets or those amazing ideas that are still in development. I wonder why we're not doing that already or why we're not offering the tools for it when we have them.³⁸

Kirby: It's good to know that if we end up with some thematic working groups or another arrangement, we have tools to support that, and the online platform can accommodate it.³⁹

Ivy: But how is the concept created, and how is it implemented in practice without centralised control, if I can challenge you a bit?⁴⁰

Alex: Even if I was onboarded to the DES initiative as a relatively new acquaintance in the data economy field, my observations are that there is so much new going on in the field that mutual understanding and know-how around certain topics are very much needed. I mean, going into more ecosystem-based operations requires a certain kind of culture. Even a cultural change.⁴¹

James: What I think is that we should invest in building networks between companies of different sizes and ...

Kirby: ... and the role of the DES would be a tool, no, better, a stepping stone for the emergence of ecosystems?⁴²

James: Well, yeah, but it's still a rather young initiative, isn't it? I mean, just thinking of how long we've been working on this ... The objectives of the DES that we set in November are still relevant, but maybe we need more discussion about those in the ER. I'd also like to discuss the objectives of our own activities and whether there are any separate instruments to be added to this initiative to enable ecosystem building. I think the practical challenge here is how to actually activate people both in the ER as well as elsewhere in the network because it's obvious that networking the companies in DES hasn't succeeded.⁴³

Joss: The main added value is the public and private sectors having a shared forum, where what's happening on the business side can be easily conveyed to the government level ... so these data spaces are built to serve the needs of Finnish companies. That's the core for me.⁴⁴

Mason: I agree. I also see that the added value comes from the fact that we're now witnessing the emergence of some kind of ecosystem accelerator, which is advancing something on a more concrete level that needs to be pushed forward in collaboration.

Max: One aspect is concreteness, which is good, but the other side is ensuring it doesn't remain disconnected. It's great that, for instance, you, Mason, are involved, as you can emphasise that Finland's will regarding the data economy and digitalisation should be aligned.⁴⁵

Mason: The word ecosystem is terribly worn out but in practice, this

³¹ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-9.

³² Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-1.

³³ Paraphrased quotes from I-5 in the workshop.

³⁴ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-1.

³⁵ Paraphrased quotes from I-5 in the second planning meeting.

³⁶ Direct quote from I-11 in the second planning meeting.

³⁷ Direct quote from I-4 in the second planning meeting.

³⁸ Paraphrased quotes from I-13 in the first planning meeting.

³⁹ Paraphrased quotes from I-11 in the first planning meeting.

⁴⁰ Paraphrased quotes from I-13 in the first planning meeting.

⁴¹ Paraphrased quote from the second-round interview with I-7.

⁴² Direct quote from the second-round interview with I-11.

⁴³ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-8.

⁴⁴ Direct quote from I-3 in the second planning meeting.

⁴⁵ Direct quotes from I-9 in the second planning meeting.

requires this kind of interconnection, at least. The types of cooperation models also need competition regulations to be clarified. In other words, what type of cooperation you can have without any worries ... The way of doing things ... That I trust all my partners and when you have the content, then basically, the projects will fly if there is an actual need and demand for them from the sector where the companies operate.⁴⁶

Joss: If we anticipate an unprecedented amount of money coming into the data economy soon to enable better, smarter, and more sustainable ways of working through digitalisation, it's significant in this context to bring the different parties together and create mutual situational awareness.⁴⁷

Terry: The small business aspect is now, of course, particularly important for Finland's competitiveness. As I mentioned earlier, the infrastructure built on the secure network of verifiable data solutions, for example, the self-sovereign identity-based wallet model, needs to be emphasised again and again: if not everyone understands its importance, then we still have work to do ... If we can't distribute this more effectively through the DES, then it's a pretty useless institution. This is the number one priority now—how to twist and turn to make it happen.⁴⁸

Jody: Well, now we've got some good perspectives laid out. There are different viewpoints here.⁴⁹ But let's take a short break, shall we?

In Scene 2, the choral exchange of the different individuals' perceptions of the function of the boundary space and the organisation of the multistakeholder initiative shows how the interaction and dynamics within the group of people manifest implicit boundary talk—the microprocesses of both *collaborative* and *configurational* boundary work—by the individuals. These types of boundary work try to resolve the tensions in their attempt at bridging sectoral boundaries to 'get [national data economy actors] to play with the same blocks' and in 'tighter cooperation' while determining the governance (e.g. state led vs. public-private) and reach of the space (e.g. domestic vs. international) to enable and facilitate potential future collaborative structures, with ecosystems being one possible outcome. The scene shows evidence of how making room (i.e. time and space) for such collaboration means consideration of each stakeholder's and individual's commitment, available resources, and leadership.

4.2.3. Scene 3—The 'midwives' delivering something new and concrete

[Jody's monologue/soliloquy; speaking aloud to oneself, but not directly to the audience; spotlight on Jody; other characters in the dark]

Jody: I think that instead of staying at the level of [air quoting] 'promise-ware', as Joss calls it,⁵⁰ the DES should lead to different actors finding or being brought into contact with each other ... This could lead to new experiments, projects, innovations, or ecosystems. Even though my employer has already gained new connections through the DES and they have led us to agreements on new experiments and follow-ups⁵¹, I think that's the part that is still largely missing.⁵² Linking the different perspectives so far has been essential, but we are after concrete actions and outcomes.

If the existing networks and projects were just better identified, we, the ER, could more soundly encourage certain topics of collaboration and serve as sort of [air quoting] 'midwives' of cooperation to deliver something new.⁵³ I think it's like Joss advocates that it's about getting entrepreneurs of small and medium enterprises to understand how the data economy relates to their business. If that happened, they would

become interested in joining and potentially finding their place among the data economy actors through the DES. They say it's a kind of circle. When we get to more concrete matters, a value proposition becomes clearer.⁵⁴

Now, I'm just wondering if we should believe Joss when he says that if any big change is needed to promote the use of data in enterprises, maybe time will take care of that when companies are a bit further along in their actions, and things will then be worked out organically.⁵⁵ This is not some kind of limited and clear-cut project, like Marley says. Instead, this started as a grassroots-type activity, done by a certain group of people, and it would be good if there was more of this exchange of ideas, perhaps also somewhat deliberately undefined so that it doesn't have so many strict performance targets, if you will ... Marley put it well that [air quoting] 'it is not worth overemphasising the roles and whose job it is to do something here as long as we just do it.'⁵⁶

However, we need to take particular care to ensure that we have the key actors, a sort of coordinating team, who will create and accelerate the change.⁵⁷ At the same time, Marley and Mason suggest that we need to involve research as well as funders together with other practice-level actors in the data economy field.⁵⁸ What I do not want is to see the DES only as the business and work of an enlightened elite that wants to push things faster towards something concrete.⁵⁹

In Scene 3, we can see the reflection of configurational boundary work by the individuals. Preferences to maintain informality in the community and its actions demarcate the boundary space—and its permeable boundaries of collaboration—as inclusive and as uncoordinated as possible without any heavy top-down agenda. The challenge then becomes how to develop a space where 'delivering' concrete added value is possible. This would require negotiation of the organisational and professional boundaries, in other words, collaborative boundary work within the coordinating body.

4.3. Act 2—ALL the delicacies set to the table – but is anyone leading this?⁶⁰

Act 2 shows evidence of how the boundary work of a multi-stakeholder initiative attempting to create a boundary space turns into a *performance* of collaborative and configurational boundary work. It shows how these two types of boundary work may be hard to keep separated when the scope and scale of the boundary space initiative are not clear.

4.3.1. Scene 1—We need some feedback

[Dialogue between Emery, Kirby, Mason, Ivy, Max and James; all the characters in the spotlight]

Emery: So. Any thoughts on how we could make the time together as effective as possible?⁶¹

Ivy: What's the goal of this collaborative work? Please, let's get to the point of what kinds of benefits can be offered to different levels of participation in DES ... How do we enable participation? Where should participation be possible ... ?⁶²

Kirby: This workshop's goal is to refine the DES concept and look for concrete actions beyond the events themselves.⁶³

Mason: There are probably expectations on many fronts, both

⁴⁶ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round of interview with I-4.

⁴⁷ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-3.

⁴⁸ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-1.

⁴⁹ Direct quotes from 2nd round interview with I-10.

⁵⁰ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-3.

⁵¹ Paraphrased quote from email between I-10 and the third author on 11th of March 2021.

⁵² Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-10.

⁵³ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round of interview with I-10.

⁵⁴ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-3.

⁵⁵ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-3.

⁵⁶ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-5.

⁵⁷ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-10.

⁵⁸ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-4 and I-5.

⁵⁹ Paraphrased quote from the second-round interview with I-3.

⁶⁰ Title of the email from I-1 to fourth author on 29th of October 2020.

⁶¹ Direct quote of I-12 from the second planning meeting.

⁶² Paraphrased quotes of I-13 from the first planning meeting.

⁶³ Paraphrased quotes of I-11 from the second planning meeting.

regarding the approach to our work and about refining the goal in the more thematic discussion about what is being aimed for with the DES. For my organisation, the ecosystem accelerator level of activity is definitely where we hope to receive feedback, including in the form of initiatives that we can further take into higher-level regulatory frameworks or otherwise contribute to the broader content.⁶⁴

Ivy: So, as the ER, you have the chance to think about how things will be done. So, we're not here to discuss what the concept will be in the future, but rather what kind of working process supports the concept development in this workshop.⁶⁵ And if I may continue ... framing the work by themes or areas of activity, here on the online platform, could be useful, and then just ... you know, start doing things. I mean, experimenting, not over-conceptualising, but also taking clear responsibility within the network. Those who actively want to take action should be given support, opportunities, tools, and so on.⁶⁶

Emery: James, you're the latest addition to the ER. It's good to have you with us to represent the Finnish entrepreneurs and the business side.⁶⁷ The association of entrepreneurs must need and the opportunities to do so, right? I refer to what Ivy said, it should come from the network itself, what they want, and where they invest.⁶⁸

Max: I could ask a small group of companies, for example ... I've probably mentioned the business committee, which includes major companies in the country, and also some small companies, about 20 in total. I could get some quick feedback if you'd like ... I don't know if James and the entrepreneurs could do something similar with their own committee.

James: Yes, it's possible to send out a small survey ...

Max: But it must be very agile. Just a few questions. If companies are going to respond, we need to be very clear about what we're asking.⁶⁹

Emery: We could consider whether we have time for that now?

James: I'd be inclined to ask them later ...⁷⁰

Ivy: I'd be happy to guide things in the direction of what level of commitment people are ready to make. Or, if they can't take full responsibility, simply lend a hand. Kirby and Emery, do you have any thoughts?⁷¹

In Scene 1, we can see what the collaborative boundary work needed when individuals are attempting to create a boundary space may sound and feel like. While the boundaries of the space are negotiated in relation to one's own work (i.e. professional and organisational boundaries), they are also embodied by occupying positions in the individuals' organisations and networks where they are creating thresholds—or junctures—of collaboration beyond themselves, that is, with other actors and stakeholders operating at the intersection of overlapping organisational and institutional spheres.

4.3.2. Scene 2—This is not our network!

[Dialogue between Kirby and Emery; spotlight on Kirby and Emery; other characters in the dark]

Kirby: There are so many demands that I'm feeling a bit overwhelmed by everything.⁷² They don't understand that this is not our network. So, if you want to create a subgroup, go ahead, ma'am, and do it!⁷³

Emery: Yes, so, the practical things are ours, but the concrete doing is not ... We cannot be the ones inviting or sending; it's a question of

resources, right? It must start with the network, what they want, and what they invest in.⁷⁴

Kirby: They don't seem to be willing to act, take responsibility, but expect someone else to do it for them ... Maybe I just need to spell out that even though we have the practical responsibility, it still isn't our network.⁷⁵

Emery: And administratively, the NA creates the working groups or thematic groups in the online platform, but anyone can take the lead ...⁷⁶

Kirby: To lead the thematic groups, we would need people who are interested, enthusiastic, passionate individuals ... How that happens, where we dig them up from, and whether they have the time and interest ... ? That's a whole different story.⁷⁷

To be honest, the thematic groups are just a glimmer in someone's eye right now. It would be good to discuss ways of participating. Participate in this, start working on your own theme, and join a theme room on the online platform. Could we someday reach the point where the network can give a statement? I'm afraid that all this organic tinkering will kill the concept ...⁷⁸

In Scene 2, we can again see some confusion about collaborative boundary work – or the lack of it – as the participants deal with the lack of mutual understanding about resources and pragmatic agreement on who will do what, including discussion of roles and responsibilities. In turn, the lack of active input and commitment makes coordination work among the stakeholders frustrating. It seems that explicitly drawing the boundaries of one's role and responsibilities in a multistakeholder initiative does not directly or simultaneously awaken others to identify with their own roles and responsibilities in the collective.

4.3.3. Scene 3—Perhaps the gloves have fallen off a bit?

[Dialogue between Kirby and Alex; spotlight on Kirby and Alex; other characters in the dark.]

Kirby: ... and then there are many of those who would like to have one thing but someone else should do it!⁷⁹ [An uneasy laugh]

Kirby: I've come to understand that leading a network, or being and acting in a network, always involves a balancing act between what is wanted from the network and what people are willing to do for the network. I haven't heard about how willing people are to do things and what they might be willing to do ...⁸⁰

Alex: Somehow, I think that this started with great passion and a great deal of thought, and then somehow it was expected and hoped that someone would take over. And now that the NA has taken over, so in a certain way perhaps the gloves have fallen off a bit, that somehow, we think that now it is in hands of someone who'll take it forward. Which, of course, is not true; you can't do that alone, and we still need a group of active people. While we want to keep developing the DES, we also want to be ready with it ... It's like we are between extremes. It's an exciting construction of contradictions!⁸¹

Kirby: One problem is that some perceive networking as one thing and others as something else. And we need to distinguish between when we lead the network and when we act together with the network. We are now thinking about the forms of the network's activities and then also about the forms of the network's steering activities, our activities as the ER. I think we have too many cooks stirring the broth!

Alex: Kirby, I have realised that allocating responsibilities and tasks in the ER as much as in the network is difficult because there is no formal

⁶⁴ Trimmed quote from I-4 from the second planning meeting.

⁶⁵ Paraphrased quotes from I-13 from the first planning meeting.

⁶⁶ Paraphrased quotes from I-13 from the first planning meeting.

⁶⁷ Paraphrased quotes from I-12 in the first planning meeting.

⁶⁸ Paraphrased quotes from I-13 in first planning meeting.

⁶⁹ Direct quotes from I-9 in the second planning meeting.

⁷⁰ Direct quotes from I-8 in the second planning meeting.

⁷¹ Paraphrased quotes from I-13 in the workshop.

⁷² Paraphrased quotes from I-11 in the workshop.

⁷³ Direct quote from I-11 in the first planning meeting.

⁷⁴ Trimmed quote from I-12 in the first planning meeting.

⁷⁵ Paraphrased quote from I-11 in the first planning meeting.

⁷⁶ Direct quote from I-12 in the workshop.

⁷⁷ Direct quote from the second-round interview with I-11.

⁷⁸ Paraphrased quotes from I-11 in the first planning meeting.

⁷⁹ Direct quote from the second-round interview with I-11.

⁸⁰ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-11.

⁸¹ Direct quotes from the second-round interview with I-7.

structure, even if we kind of work in a teamwork manner. You know I want to avoid forcing any structure onto something that is working without one, but I understand your pain in trying to lead and facilitate the organising work. Maybe we can separate the contract structure on paper from the organisational structure?⁸²

Kirby: Yes, I do think the ER ought to somehow formalise the DES and dedicate resources to it. We need continuity to be able to build a permanent structure ...

Alex: So, structure without heavy dust? I think the DES's structure needs to be robust but lightweight enough because we don't want anyone to feel obligated to be involved, right? If we could just keep the DES fresh and hobby-like so that those people who love the game are the ones who become involved.⁸³

Kirby: Alex, I love the idea, but we can only hope for a miracle if we want the group to be so organic and self-organised that it doesn't need a leader or anything else. That everything just happens and always hits the goal in some strange way. But I doubt it. But you should have the patience to let things build ...⁸⁴

In Scene 3, we observe how tensions impede hopes of letting things emerge in a voluntary and uncoordinated manner and require further negotiation of boundaries. The question remains whether the volunteerism and informality of a multistakeholder initiative risk the well-intended bottom-up creation of a boundary space. Configurational boundary work, such as adding structure (e.g. forms of the network's activities and forms of the network's steering activities) to how a boundary space is organised and led by a group of individuals, like the ER, challenges the ideal of a space as inclusive and with as little hierarchy and regulation as possible for the different stakeholders to collaborate.

4.4. Act 3—SILENCE

Act 3 shows how the boundary work of a multistakeholder initiative attempting to create a boundary space turns into a repetitive playact of silence and suspension.

4.4.1. Scene 1—Suspending

[Dialogue between Jody and Ivy; spotlight on all characters]

Jody: I think it's worth considering that people should be free to come and follow a theme from whatever angle they want. But that doesn't mean there couldn't be something alongside it, for example, could people find each other, discuss things separately? And then, projects could emerge that start their work in parallel with or between the DES events. But since this kind of activity always relies on volunteerism, there should be some kinds of leaders or facilitators for it. And I remind you that roles can change—it's not always forever. Personally, I don't have time for this. I can't take that role.⁸⁵

Ivy: Should we now go ahead and identify where there might be interest in taking responsibility? I believe in enthusiasm and motivation as the driving factors—many networks operate this way, especially ones that rely on a bit of voluntary effort. So?⁸⁶

[All wait for 19 s in awkward silence ...]⁸⁷

In Scene 1, we display how individuals mute or hit break at the question of what and how much to contribute personally, that is, when they would need to make decisions about efforts to develop the space in practice and work concretely towards the common objectives.

4.4.2. Scene 2⁸⁸—Speeding up

[The scene has a sense of hurry. Dialogue between Jody, Terry, Mason, Kirby, Emery and Max; spotlight on all characters.]

Jody: This is usually the moment when everyone raises their hands—when it's asked who'll do something ...

[Jody and Terry laugh amused]

Terry: I raised my hand, just as a generalist here. But what's obvious to me is that, for example, we could ask the Citizen Data initiative to join, and they, together with the public sector, could establish a regulation-influencing thematic group. In terms of regulation, we've done a really good job in Finland, heading in the right direction. Then ... [Mason interrupts]

Mason: Just a quick comment on regulation—we are happy to take ownership of that; we work bilaterally with the NA and the Citizen Data initiative, as they help with activities like webinar work. However, the regulation issues are quite firmly established in the government coordination group for the data economy. So, long story short, I wouldn't bring regulation to the DES—it's a bit tricky. But of course, this network needs to get a general overview, along with funding information.

Terry: OK then, how about soft infrastructure? That's a joint public-private matter with the Fair Data cooperative. We can invite them to take the lead in explaining this whole concept so that everyone understands its groundbreaking phase ... I can ask them, but I'm not a member of the cooperative, so I can't promise anything. They themselves need to decide whether they want to come. When is the next event?

Jody: Wasn't it in June?

Kirby: June is a bit challenging. In the NA, we have all these other obligations, wrapping up old projects and launching new themes. So, I'd suggest postponing the June event to avoid too much overlap with similar offerings. Anyway, we haven't started planning June in detail yet. Shall we move on now to discuss the DES's procedures—we're running out of time.

Terry: OK, yeah, I don't want to push it if there's no interest. But I still think it should be given some priority. We can postpone it for later, I guess ... I can ask if they're interested, but it's like there's no formal invitation [Terry's voice has a tense sound to it. There's a brief silence.]

Emery: As soon as they confirm, we could announce it on the online platform.

Max: We should also get the public funder strongly involved here. They're also trying to create a platform for companies to prepare for funding applications. So, we could at least take a look to avoid any overlap.

Emery: It's certainly important to avoid duplication. Since you're involved with a public funder ... Could you book a meeting with them and invite us all, and those who feel it's relevant to them can join?

Max: It's dangerous to speak up here—now I've been assigned the task! [chuckling] But yeah, I'll arrange a meeting, let's see.

Emery: Great, thanks. That's the whole point—to figure out how to move forward in concrete ways.

[Everyone laughs]

Emery: But we're running out of time ... We only have 3 min left, so I'll hand the floor to Kirby.

Kirby: So, I'll continue with operating procedures of the DES. We haven't yet fully planned the fall. We wrapped up the spring quite well. But I wonder how we want to continue this collaboration—should we hold monthly meetings?

[A short silence]

Kirby: OK, I'll take that as 'no comment'. Well then, what's the best channel for exchanging ideas? Should we, for example, make the Teams channel more active?

Jody: Yes, LEE set up the Teams channel earlier. We could enhance and continue using it. Or [with a small pause], does everyone feel like

⁸² Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-7.

⁸³ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-7.

⁸⁴ Paraphrased quotes from the second-round interview with I-11.

⁸⁵ Paraphrased quote from I-10 in the workshop.

⁸⁶ Direct quote from I-13 in the workshop.

⁸⁷ The factual amount of time all participants remained silent in the workshop after I-13's question.

⁸⁸ Scene based on data from the workshop.

this online platform is better?

Kirby: I don't personally mind what the format is if we just decide on something. [in a hastened tone]. That would help me a lot in handling practical matters.

Jody: I suggest using the online platform since there's already experience with it, and the Teams channel has been quiet. But let's vote on the format of the meetings later ...

[People murmur their agreement]

Emery: Now that we've heard a lot of good ideas and even concrete suggestions, if anyone feels like they want to take on a theme and advance it or is already doing it a lot through their other work, please go ahead and do it and let us know that you'll take on that task.

Kirby: Thanks for the meeting, we've moved things forward a bit. Let's continue the discussion on the online platform.

Everyone: Thank you! Bye!

[Spotlight turns off; all characters, except for Kirby, leave the stage and disappear into the dark]

Scene 2 is interlaced with work *for*, *at*, and *through* (institutional and organisational) boundaries. When articulating certain junctures between stakeholders that operate in different organisational and institutional spheres, the focal individuals temporarily perform *competitive* boundary work by embodying the competing positions of different stakeholders in attempting to create boundaries for the space through instances such as regulation, financing, and infrastructure.

4.5. FINAL ACT—Five months later

With this final act, we conclude that, ultimately, the tensions within the attempt to create boundary space will unravel boundary work at the individual level. Individuals are faced with both trade-offs and boundary work when working in and between several competing projects and priorities. By suspending repeatedly, the boundaries of the boundary space as well as their collaboration are left undefined and open.

[Monologue of Kirby; spotlight on Kirby.]

Kirby: Almost two weeks since I sent the email to them. Just a simple question asking their opinion about the themes for the November and December events ...⁸⁹

[Sigh]

It's like last January when I prepared the spring programme outline based on our planning meeting. I emailed it to them, saying, [air quoting] 'here's what we agreed on, and I'll schedule these dates; does everything look good, and are we all on the same page that I've understood this correctly?' Out of eight people, maybe two responded with 'okay' ...⁹⁰ Well, at least five out of ten reacted to this one after I sent a reminder.

Wiley, Joss, and Mason would like to highlight the EU-level issues. Covering all of it is impossible, but maybe we could introduce the topic from the company's perspective ... Max was also interested in our new public-private data space project that the NA is part of. That's great, we could use the DES as a platform to introduce our new initiatives to the wider public of data economy actors. Then, we'll have the new project manager coming in as well, I assume ...

I liked Jody's suggestion of discussing what the data economy means at the concrete level, like what the prerequisites and benefits are when thinking of the different parties involved ... But Jody directly declines my request to take responsibility for preparing the November event ... I get the point in the email that [air quoting] 'we should choose the themes for the events in one way or another together, and then choose a person or team to prepare for that theme in more detail like Kirby has been doing before'.⁹¹ And I do understand that Jody's turned it down

because of a limited capacity to take on additional work beyond a new project⁹² that is taking up all the time, therefore Jody's contribution to the DES changes, but ... how come it always ends up with someone else doing the concrete things here?

5. Discussion and conclusions

With this study, we explore the following research questions: what tensions underlie the attempt to create boundary space, and how does demarcating boundaries become a performative act to resolve these tensions? To answer these questions, we set out to study the case of the ER, a multistakeholder initiative attempting to create a space to help identify, align and ultimately integrate the interdependent activities of data economy actors across different industries, public institutions, associations and communities in Finland. First, our findings illustrate alternative perspectives that focal individuals may embody when they are attempting to collectively create a boundary space. These alternative perspectives result in tensions in and between the individuals (see Table 3). Second, to open up the felt-sense of these tensions, we constructed a theatrical script that further reveals a multivocal performance of boundary work.

By taking note of the interaction among the participants in the multistakeholder initiative – that is, the ER – we were able to highlight the individuals' roles and influences on the process of making sense and making decisions regarding the focal initiative, not least their roles in preventing the initiative from moving forward. What then becomes apparent is that the different voices in the demarcation of boundaries start to showcase not only the nuances of the multiple tensions that relate to the more pragmatic as well as the more idealistic perceptions of what and how organising a boundary space in the data economy context could and/or should be, but also the types of boundary work that such tensions require. Furthermore, the script showcases how the different embedded voices and meaningful silences in the creation process instantiate temporary and repetitive turns of boundary work, suspension and delay. These temporal and repetitive turns may both be the result of the tensions and explain why the tensions are not resolved. Yet, the tensions and suspension(s) not only emphasise the multivocality in the interaction and dynamics of the multistakeholder initiative, but also, more importantly, the performative side of individuals' boundary work.

Our approach also enabled us to explore some of the subtleties of the interpenetration among the different types of boundary work (see Langley et al., 2019) and show their entanglement and dynamics as interlaced and scarcely separable elements. For example, while some individuals are doing collaborative boundary work, such as by negotiating and aligning organisational and professional boundaries by discussing pragmatic issues on actions, resources and roles, others may still be trying to work through organisational or institutional boundaries between different initiatives and activities of which the individuals are part. Thus, these individuals continuously return to the configurational type of boundary work and questions, such as what must be prioritised, who the space is serving and how, where and when to put resources. The individuals' preoccupation with working *through* organisational and institutional boundaries diverts their focus from the work *at* the organisational and professional boundaries needed to develop the boundary space in the first place.

5.1. Theoretical contributions

Our study shows how latent tensions within a (multistakeholder) group become salient (cf. Smith and Lewis, 2011) in a more interactive setting, and how social relations in situ begin to demarcate the boundaries (Weinfurter and Seidl, 2019) of a boundary space. Based on our findings, we argue that by observing and analysing a multistakeholder

⁸⁹ Paraphrased from I-11's email to the ER on 4th of October.

⁹⁰ Paraphrased quotes from I-11 in a meeting with the third author.

⁹¹ Direct quote from I-10's email to the ER on 4th of October.

⁹² Paraphrased from I-10's email to the ER on 4th of October.

initiative only at the multistakeholder level and focusing on tensions and organisational and institutional boundaries, we risk missing out on important micro-level insights that inform us about tensions relating to the focal individuals' perspectives of what is central and preferable in the process. Even if mundane, the individuals' professional boundaries related to their mental frames and motivations and based on their perception of their roles, workloads and time horizons, are critical in attempts to create boundary space vis-à-vis others. The tensions emerging from individuals' varying perceptions (e.g. about timeframes) and positions in the collaborative context matter in terms of how they prioritise and conduct day-to-day work (cf. Peetz and Wohl, 2019) and, hence, in the effort they put into thinking and organising for collective action – both envisioning and concretely working towards it. These tensions then begin to show the micro-dynamics of creating a boundary space and shift our attention to the different individual voices and their dynamism embedded in such a process.

First, we contribute to research on the microfoundations of boundary space (Champenois and Etzkowitz, 2018) by highlighting situated and collective interactions as significant processes underlying the creation of boundary spaces. Our work follows calls for more research on micro-interaction dynamics (Furnari, 2014; Gray et al., 2015) and complements previous findings on individual determinants in boundary work enabling collaborative innovation (Bertello et al., 2022). By conceptualising boundary spaces as products of (inter)action, rather than as given, or as material and static 'containers' of collaboration (cf. Ungureanu et al., 2021, p. 1003), we may begin to see how such spaces initially exist via the competitive, collaborative and configurational boundary work carried out by individuals. Hence, we suggest that by seeing the different boundaries (i.e. professional, organisational and institutional) involved in creating space not as fixed structures, but as means and outcomes of ongoing negotiation, collaboration, or contestation – even suspension – we can approach related boundary work as a continuous activity of performing those boundaries and integral to the unfolding of a space (cf. Lefebvre, 1991; Steigenberger and Lübcke, 2022; Beyes and Holt, 2020; Ratner, 2020).

Second, by looking at microinteractions (e.g. Kouamé and Langley, 2018; Patriotta and Spedale, 2011), we show how the social dynamics in the boundary work process may overshadow or impede what individuals personally aim to accomplish. To this end, we stress that boundary work becomes performed vis-à-vis other people and may delay or suspend the focal process. In other words, achieving a 'collective mind' is not a given; and instead, collective efforts to create boundary space may remain in flux, unable to resolve tension over long periods (Gray et al., 2015, p. 117; see also Weick and Roberts, 1993).

Third, our research shows how the mundane and everyday dynamics and interactions in performing boundary work is perhaps more 'pre-reflexive', that is, more unintentional than intentional (Langley et al., 2019, p. 727). Our fine-grained approach adds to the configurational boundary work literature by enriching a study domain that is usually undertaken at a more abstract, or coarse-grained, level and to the over-intellectualising of collaborative boundary work literature, which often overlooks emotions stirred by boundary work (Langley et al., 2019). In addition, our findings show how individuals are performing boundary work versus being aware of, making sense of, or even having practices (Lindberg et al., 2017) of doing such work. What we see in our data is a reflective episode (Krautzbeger and Tuckermann, 2024), where the ER members were temporarily separated from the ongoing daily activities and practices (Hendry and Seidl, 2003; Bucher and Langley, 2016) of their employing organisations and became somewhat aware of the contradicting demands they were making of the DES and its organisation. We suggest that boundary work is emergent, somewhat implicit, and remains performative when it is not an explicit objective or conscious practice.

5.2. Methodological contributions

Our second set of contributions relates largely to our methodological approach and microprocessual perspective. Narrative analysis and ethnodrama 'open up the narrative possibilities' (Rhodes and Brown, 2005, p. 473), enabling us to elucidate the contextual nature of the tensions and boundary work without compromising the complexity, richness and nuances of the qualitative data (see also Langley et al., 2023). In addition, our methodological choices afforded us the possibility of 'making microfoundations come more alive' and address the challenge of realising them empirically (Felin et al., 2015, p. 578).

Our paper showcases how different types of boundary work are understood through an ethnodrama, a written play script based on the dramatisation of the diverse set of data. By presenting our findings as an ethnodramatic script accompanied by thick description, we address how different types of boundary work (e.g. Langley et al., 2019) may be difficult to see clearly in practice and challenging to articulate purely in a more traditional research report. The ongoing dynamics at the individual, organisational and institutional levels create tensions and interdependencies, and such tensions result in ongoing parallel, even multiplex, boundary work (cf. Bertello et al., 2022; Ungureanu et al., 2021; Peschl and Fundneider, 2014). Through our dramaturgical analysis, we noticed how the workshop meetings (as microinteraction situations) between the ER members became a setting for accentuated boundary work and, hence, an opportunity for us to explore and show the ongoing performative side of boundary work (Lindberg et al., 2017), and the nuances of the interaction dynamics involved (Patriotta and Spedale, 2011).

We argue that while the word *performance* in boundary work literature has merely indicated the conducting or doing of boundary work (see e.g. Langley et al., 2019), with a novel reading of performance and the ongoing performing of boundary work as a performative act, we may begin to highlight the drama (Saldaña, 2011) in interaction dynamics between the parties/actors involved. To this end, our study shows how a multistakeholder initiative demarcates boundaries for a space through the stakeholders' actions and language. Namely, we show that boundary work comes through powerfully in both individuals' linguistic choices (e.g. metaphors) and their performative acts in the interaction situation (e.g. emotional clues, ironic comments, meaningful silences, repetition and meta-talk about why they take certain stances or perspectives).

5.3. Practical implications

Our research approaches the mundane practices in everyday work related to multistakeholder initiatives and cross-sectoral collaboration. With our study and findings, we provide practitioners with a deeper understanding of the 'micro-level interactions that are often understudied or forgotten, and the way in which they can be consequential' (Kouamé and Langley, 2018, p. 573). Although the data economy represents a special type of empirical setting, we argue that our findings are transferable beyond this context (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). For example, our findings might resonate with collaborative, cross-sector initiatives that struggle to navigate or manage complex societal issues such as climate change, urban planning or migration (Palmer et al., 2025). They can be relevant more broadly for interdisciplinary collaboration (Ese and Ese, 2022), intra- and interprofessional multidisciplinary teams (Ungureanu and Bertolotti, 2018; Comeau-Vallée and Langley, 2019), as well as social movements (Daykin, 2019). Indeed, silence and suspension are both transferable and relatable issues in various attempts to do collaborative work, but at the same time they are useful observations in trying to understand the pace, realities and outlines of creating a boundary space (i.e. inclusion/exclusion, policy work and regulations), not least the crucial role that single individuals may play. We are convinced that the presence of deep contextual detail facilitates our readers' evaluation of whether our findings resonate with their experience in other situations (see also Kouamé and Langley, 2017). While our

study does not offer 'obvious and simple normative prescriptions', it provides the felt-sense of boundary work and encourages practitioners to think reflexively about their own practices, offering potential for generative learning (ibid., p. 574).

Performing collaborative boundary work within and between organisations concerns creating clear but flexible boundaries that help people work together without unnecessary tensions and conflict. An increased understanding of negotiating boundaries of who does what – that is, how to share responsibilities – helps practitioners to act as translators or bridges in setting the rules for engagement. Embodying the boundary between organisations means both working across organisations and holding them together, which helps align individual and collective goals. Here, the notion of boundary space as liminoid highlights the possibilities to temporarily show up with less defined roles and boundaries, which are later re-established for collective action. Moreover, performing configurational boundary work allows the setting up of boundaries that encourage collaboration and separate functions where independence is beneficial. Thus, an increased understanding of performing boundary work and tensions in creating boundary space will advance practitioners' capabilities to consciously reflect and interact across different roles, ensuring smoother collaboration and better outcomes.

5.4. Limitations and future research

The limitations of this work stem from its exploratory nature, which is bound to the time and space of a single initiative in Finland, a small and highly digitised country (Finnish Government, 2022). However, we think it is worth accepting the limitations associated with the context-specificity and transferability of our findings because we have gained an in-depth understanding of the focal case. Despite its limitations, our study offers novel insights into the tensions and boundary work involved in creating space – not least because of our methodological choices. Our study suggests several possible research avenues to address some of the limitations of this research. We recognise that our study suffers from a post hoc approach to the case study, especially in its use of interactive data, as this approach delimits our full inclusion of the processual approach into the research strategy. Consequently, we had to rely on data sources that we did not strategically collect for a longitudinal case study, and therefore richer notes on the more implicit nature and the felt sense of certain events (e.g. meetings) did not exist.

Future research could and should, therefore, engage with a genuine hand-in-hand longitudinal ethnographic or micro-ethnographic process to study the creation of a boundary space to further understand how boundary work is performed to resolve tensions. Whereas our study portrays individual-level tensions and the build-up and dynamics of the interactions and (counter)actions between informants, future research could go beyond the focal collective to capture the most influential ways of performing boundary work in the process of creating a boundary space longitudinally. We believe that more qualitative (micro)processual research and applicable designs focusing on human interaction and dynamics would further strengthen the understanding and visibility of micro-macro linkages and the processes or mechanisms through which they appear (Kouamé and Langley, 2018).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Argyro Almpapoulou: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Satu Vesin:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Pia Adibe:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Kirsimarja Blomqvist:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

None.

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Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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